

Deliverable D6.9.

Pilot (IT) Technical report and achieved results (2 | 2)

Deliverable report

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BWI	Bond Work Index
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
DDE	Dynamic Data Exchange DDE
DEQ	DigiEcoQuarry
DoA	Description of Action
DWH	Data Warehouse
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HMD	Hydrometallurgy Division
IFS	Individual Financial Statement
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KTA	Key Technology Areas
LCSI	Local Crushing and Screening Interface
MAC	Measurement and Control Division
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
MPD	Mineral Processing Division
PFSIGN	Project Financial Statement
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
RCSI	Remote Crushing and Screening Interface
RP	Reporting Period
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
PRC	Project Research Committee
WP	Work Package

1 Pilot overview

The Pioltello quarry, located near Milan, serves as a pilot site for Holcim's DigiEcoQuarry initiative. This site features a crushing and screening plant for aggregates production, along with a dredge for excavating alluvial material. The crushing and screening plant is the primary focus of the DigiEcoQuarry implementation.

DigiEcoQuarry Activities at Pioltello:

As outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), the Pioltello pilot site is actively implementing a series of activities aligned with specific tasks and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across Work Packages (WPs) 2 to 5:

WP2: Crushing and Screening Optimization:

- High-resolution models: Development and implementation of high-resolution models to optimize crushing and screening processes.

WP3: Treatment and Processing:

- Automation devices: Integration of devices for automating the treatment plant, enhancing efficiency and reducing manual intervention.
- Monitoring sensors and analysis tools: Deployment of sensors on mobile machinery to monitor performance, collect data, and provide insights for analysis.

WP4: Digital Platform and Technologies:

- Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS): Implementation and deployment of a central data management platform integrating various digital technologies (Data Lake, Data integration, Dashboards), expert systems (production control system, Environmental simulation platform) and providing business management tools.
- BIM (Building Information Modelling): Implementation of BIM models to create a digital representation of the quarry, facilitating planning, design, and construction.
- Artificial Intelligence algorithms: Development and application of AI algorithms for various tasks, such as stockpile volume calculation and process optimization.

WP5: H&S and Environmental Management:

- H&S technologies: Integration of technologies to enhance health and safety practices within the quarry.
- Environmental simulation platform: Development and use of a platform to simulate environmental impacts and optimize environmental performance.

Moreover, all the pilot, included Pioltello, gave horizontally their contribution also in **WP7** (mechanism for social acceptance), **WP8** (clustering activities) and **WP9** (dissemination, communication and exploitation) with many actions that contributed to the fulfilment of the project intentions.

Holcim's Leadership Role:

In addition to its own pilot site activities, Holcim, as the group leader of WP6, plays a crucial role in coordinating the DigiEcoQuarry initiative across all pilot sites. This includes:

- Monitoring ongoing activities: Tracking the progress of activities at all pilot sites.
- Ensuring timeline adherence: Monitoring the respect of timelines and deadlines for each task.
- Organizing periodic meetings: Facilitating regular meetings to update progress, share best practices, and address challenges.

Overall, the Pioltello quarry serves as a testing ground for the DigiEcoQuarry initiative, showcasing the potential of digital technologies to optimize operations, enhance safety, and improve environmental performance in the quarrying industry. Holcim's leadership role in WP6 ensures the successful implementation and coordination of the initiative across all participating sites.

Figure 1. Drone view of Pioltello pilot site.

2 Implementation of technologies

The second phase, from M14 to M46, starting from the application and installation of the sensors on the Pioltello plant, involved the following application phases:

- Connection of the installed sensors to the SCADA /Data Lake application.
- Continuous detection of data sent by sensors.
- Analysis and evaluation of the data collected.
- Continuous maintenance of the installed sensors.

2.1 Models for crushing and screening optimization (Task 2.7)

MINTEK's contribution to Task 2.7 aims at developing breakage and screening models, obtaining online Particle Size Distribution (PSD) measurements, designing and implementing a Remote Crushing and Screening Interface (RCSI) and a Local Crushing and Screening Interface (LCSI, located at the HOLCIM site and being linked to the Data Lake and RCSI). These different components facilitate the creation of a digital twin of a crushing-screening circuit and the use of the twin for plant optimization through changes in certain operational parameters without interfering with the production of the physical plant.

MINTEK performed these tasks in three of its divisions: the Mineral Processing Division (MPD), the Hydrometallurgy Division (HMD) and the Measurement and Control Division (MAC).

The following figure shows a subsection of the HOLCIM facility flowchart with the MINTEK area simulated using the digital twin bordered by a red dashed border. The main components of this section are the storage silo, the cone crusher, the vibrating screens and the recycling split.

Figure 2. Section of the process flow diagram for HOLCIM with the sub-section to be simulated enclosed by the red-dashed line.

Starting from this scheme, a digital twin model was created to allow simulations to be carried out for the optimization of the plant through the modification of some operating parameters without interfering with the production of the physical plant.

MINTEK devised the following plan of action to accomplish its task:

Figure 3. Flowchart depicting the various tasks undertaken by MINTEK in relation to current project.

All the operations conducted by MINTEK to achieve the intended objectives have been described in document D2.10 to which please refer for further details.

2.1.1 Task conducted on Pioltello site

HOLCIM sent two pallets with two drums each containing approximately 700 – 740 kg of aggregate sample material to MINTEK (Figure 4). The materials were sampled from the plant’s conveyor belts transporting materials to and from the crusher. The samples were analysed for MINTEK mineralogical and physical characteristics.

Figure 4. Two pallets with two drums containing aggregate sample material sent by HOLCIM to MINTEK for analysis.

After the collection of the samples and the shipping to MINTEK, HOLCIM started with the installation of two PSD (Particle Size Detection) sensors for granulometry measurement has been performed on week 15-19 May from HOLCIM.

In the first stage, one PSD sensor has been installed inside the tunnel, which is the stockpile of material feeding the plant.

Figure 5. PSD sensor installed in the tunnel in Pioltello plant.

It was decided to modify the point of installation, since from that point it was not possible to link the granulometry with the crushing process, because between the PSD sensor and the crusher, there is a vibrating screen which modifies the granulometry of the material.

After removing the sensor from the tunnel, one sensor was placed on the conveyor belt before the main cone crusher, while the other was installed on the belt placed after the crusher. Thus, the two PSD sensors acquire and analyse data regarding the input/output material of the main cone crusher. The sensors are running, and data are ready to be transferred to Data Lake.

Together with the camera, which is the core of the vision system, also two stripes of led lights have been installed. The lights can be turned on/off from PLC, allowing to test if better results are achieved with natural or artificial lighting.

The system gives output data regarding the distribution of the aggregates sizes. This granulometry line can be plotted on a graph representing the cumulative percentage distribution of the material, both for natural and crushed aggregates.

Figure 6. Q-vision sensors, supplied by MA-ESTRO for the granulometry detection of material before and after the main cone crusher

Figure 7. Processing of the images acquired by the 2 PDS sensors for the granulometry detection.

Figure 8. Plotted data of the PSD for the material before the crushing (left) and after the crushing (right).

Figure 9. Comparison of the fineness modules entering the mill (black curve) and exiting the mill (blue curve).

In addition, a weigh system has been installed on the conveyor belt placed after the cone crusher (the same where one of the two PSD sensors is installed). The system has been supplied by ARCO and is described in the next chapter. It allows to acquire additional information for the creation of the crushing models.

The primary crushing process was enhanced by integrating q-vision sensors at the input and output, along with a weighing system on the conveyor belt. This setup enabled better control and optimization of the crushing process. As a result, the efficiency of the cone crusher (Metso) was improved controlling the absorption of the machine. The plant manager directly monitored and managed the crushing process using the MAESTRO SCADA PC, maintaining a consistent range regulation.

Whenever a misalignment was detected (indicated by a red circle), corrective adjustments were made to the crusher to restore optimal crushing conditions.

In general, the use of this technology proved useful for the primary crushing process, although some critical issues were detected, mainly related to the strong vibrations of the system, which made it necessary to pay greater attention to the Q-vision cameras, which had to undergo heavy maintenance to allow their use.

2.2 Production control system and automation (Task 3.2)

This document outlines the data acquisition and management system implemented at the Pioltello plant in collaboration with MAESTRO, a provider of sensors and automation solutions.

Installation and Data Acquisition:

- The installation phase was completed in June 2022.
- MAESTRO supplied sensors and automation systems for the plant.
- A comprehensive sensor list, positioning, and status are maintained through periodic updates of the Pioltello plant flowsheet (see Annex I).
- Data acquired from the sensors is processed and made accessible through MAESTRO's portal.

Main data Access and Reporting:

- The MAESTRO portal provides access to various data points, including for example:
 - Cumulative production volumes.
 - Production rate per aggregate type.
 - Working time (start and stop times).
 - Granulometry of incoming material (sensed by the Q-vision system).
 - Electrical consumption.
- This data is organized into daily and annual datasheets, stored in historical reports, and sent to the Data Lake for access by interested partners.

Key Benefits:

- The data acquisition and management system provide a comprehensive overview of plant operations.
- Real-time data access enables informed decision-making and process optimization.
- Historical data analysis supports trend identification and performance improvement.
- Data sharing through the Data Lake facilitates collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders.

Figure 10. Synoptic picture of Pioltello plant from MAESTRO's portal.

Below there is a list of the sensors, what they measure and the KPIs they act on. Following, there is a brief description of each sensor type.

Table 1. List of sensors installed on Pioltello site.

Qty	Sensor	Measuring Unit	Energy	Water	Efficiency	m ³ H ₂ O / ton	kWh / ton
2	Q-vision	t/h	x				x
8	Volumetric Sensor	m ³ /h			x		
2	Weight system	t/h			x		
4	Pressure transducer	bar		x		x	
1	Temperature sensor	degrees			x		
5	Vibration sensor	amplitude, frequency	x				x
4	Anti-skid sensor	i/o			x		
2	Pump litre counter	litres, m ³		x		x	
3	Camera	image			x		
10	Electric Transducer (TA)	amper	x				x
8	Anti-sticking sensor	radar			x		
2	Level sensor	% capacity			x		
27	Rotation control	Pulse counter			X		
1	Power centre absorption	kWh	x				x

2.2.1 Anti-skid sensors

Anti-skid sensors play a crucial role in optimizing belt conveyor systems by detecting and preventing belt slippage. These sensors, strategically positioned on either side of the belt, provide a two-tiered warning system to safeguard against potential damage and downtime.

Early Detection and Prevention:

The first level of warning alerts operators when the belt is not properly centred on the roller drum. This early detection allows for timely adjustments, preventing the belt from slipping further and potentially causing damage.

Protecting Against Catastrophic Failure:

The second level of warning triggers when the belt has slipped to a point where it is at risk of tearing. This critical alert prompts immediate intervention, preventing costly repairs and production delays.

Benefits of Anti-Skid Sensors:

- **Reduced Maintenance:** Early detection and intervention minimize the need for extensive repairs, reducing maintenance costs and downtime.
- **Increased Efficiency:** By preventing belt damage and ensuring smooth operation, anti-skid sensors contribute to increased production efficiency.
- **Enhanced Safety:** The warning system alerts operators to potential hazards, promoting a safer working environment.

Figure 11. Anti-skid sensor for detection of undesired side-motion of the belt.

The integration of these sensors was crucial for the DEQ project. They were installed on the main conveyor belts feeding the total amount of raw materials to the washing screening and crushing phase. The recommendation and the opportunity for further optimisation in the following years will be the installation of these sensors also on the excavation phase (floating and land conveyors belt) excluded in this project for Pioltello site. The only critical aspect related to the sensor's operation is the potential presence of material falling off the belt, which could hinder its functionality. Therefore, it is essential to keep the area surrounding the sensor installation point clean.

2.2.2 Volumetric sensors

Eight volumetric sensors are strategically placed atop each unloading conveyor belt. These sensors work in tandem with rotation sensors to accurately measure material volume. The volumetric sensors scan the incoming material profile, while the rotation sensors track the conveyor belt speed. This combined data allows for precise calculation of the volume unloaded into each stockpile, providing production volumes for each aggregate type.

Figure 12. Volumetric sensor installed on the top of an unloading conveyor belt.

Advantages of Volumetric Sensors:

- Real-time Data: Instantaneous and cumulative material flows are readily accessible through the MAESTRO portal, providing real-time insights into production processes.
- Non-Contact Measurement: Unlike traditional weighbridge systems, volumetric sensors operate without physical contact with the conveyor belt, eliminating wear points and reducing maintenance requirements.

Challenges and Mitigation Strategies:

- Water Reflections: The system is susceptible to water reflections, which can affect accuracy. To address this, we are experimenting with reducing conveyor belt speed by adjusting pulleys. This allows water more time to drain, potentially mitigating the reflection issue.

Precision Monitoring and Calibration:

To ensure the accuracy of the volumetric sensors, a comprehensive monitoring system is in place. This involves comparing the volumes measured by the sensors with data obtained from GPS surveys of the stockpiles and sales volumes. An operator walks across the stockpiles, collecting a cloud of georeferenced points (coordinates and altitude). Specialized software processes the collected data to generate a 3D mesh representing the stockpile's shape. The 3D mesh allows for precise calculation of the stockpile's volume.

Since GPS surveys are conducted monthly, the calibration process is performed on a monthly basis, ensuring ongoing accuracy of the volumetric sensor data.

The integration of these sensors was significant for the DEQ project, allowing us to have real-time data on the MAESTRO management system for quantifying all finished products. This data was also cross-checked with physical measurements taken on the ground of the stockpiles. (See paragraph 2.5.1) This type of volumetric sensor proved more effective for granular products than for fine products. The only critical aspect observed for alluvial materials and our processing methods is that the measurement can be affected by the presence of water, either from the material itself or from the atmosphere in case of rain, which flows on the conveyor belt and, near the laser beam, can produce refraction that affect the measurements.

2.2.3 Pump litre counters

Pump litre counters, strategically placed on both the fresh water extraction pipeline and the recirculating water supply line, provide valuable insights into water consumption within industrial plants. This data empowers operators to monitor and optimize water usage, ultimately reducing reliance on freshwater sources.

Monitoring Fresh Water Consumption:

The litre counter on the freshwater extraction pipeline provides a precise measurement of the amount of freshwater being drawn into the plant. This data allows for accurate tracking of overall water consumption and identification of potential areas for improvement.

Assessing Recirculation Efficiency:

The litre counter on the recirculating water supply line measures the volume of water being reused within the plant. This data reveals the efficiency of the recirculation system and highlights opportunities to optimize water reuse practices.

Benefits of Pump Litre Counters:

- **Water Conservation:** By monitoring both fresh and recirculated water usage, operators can identify areas where freshwater consumption can be reduced.
- **Cost Savings:** Reducing freshwater consumption translates into lower water bills and potentially reduced treatment costs.
- **Environmental Sustainability:** Minimizing reliance on freshwater sources contributes to responsible water management and environmental sustainability.

Figure 13. Liter counter installed on recirculating water pipeline.

The inclusion of this type of sensor was crucial and very useful for accurately evaluating the amount of freshwater and recycled water used in the material processing operations. A key element of this system is the calibration of the sensor for the correct reading of data directly on the MAESTRO SCADA/Data Lake.

2.2.4 Pressure sensors

Pressure sensors, strategically mounted on the top of water cyclones, play a crucial role in optimizing the performance of these essential separation devices. By monitoring pressure levels, operators can fine-tune cyclone operation, leading to reduced water consumption and increased efficiency.

Function:

Water cyclones utilize centrifugal force to separate fine materials, such as sand, from dirty water. The pressure within the cyclone directly influences the separation process, impacting the efficiency of particle removal and the volume of water required.

Pressure Sensor Role:

Pressure sensors mounted on the top of the cyclone provide real-time data on the pressure within the system. This data allows operators to:

- Monitor Cyclone Performance: Pressure fluctuations indicate changes in the separation process, alerting operators to potential issues.
- Optimize Water Consumption: By adjusting the pressure, operators can fine-tune the separation process to minimize water usage while maintaining effective particle removal.
- Increase Efficiency: Optimizing pressure levels ensures efficient separation, maximizing the removal of fine materials and minimizing the need for additional processing.

Benefits of Pressure Sensors:

- Water Conservation: Precise pressure control minimizes water consumption, reducing operational costs and environmental impact.
- Improved Efficiency: Optimized pressure levels enhance the separation process, leading to higher particle removal rates and reduced waste.
- Predictive Maintenance: Monitoring pressure trends can identify potential issues before they become major problems, reducing downtime and maintenance costs.

Figure 14. Pressure sensor mounted on two water cyclones.

Figure 15. Annual pressure detected of the water cyclone.

The placement of these sensors mounted on the cyclones allows for monitoring the proper functioning of the machine. Too low pressure indicates a potential malfunction of the impeller, leading to excessive loss of fine material. This necessitates maintenance intervention for impeller replacement.

2.2.5 Electric transducers

Electric transducers, positioned within the electrical cabinet, monitoring the current absorption of critical machinery like crushers, pumps, and screens. This real-time data empowers operators to optimize machine performance, leading to significant energy savings and improved operational efficiency.

Monitoring Current Absorption

Current absorption, as depicted in the provided figure, serves as a vital indicator of machine performance. By analysing current fluctuations, operators can:

- Identify Overloading: Abnormal spikes in current absorption signal potential overloading, indicating a need for adjustments or maintenance.
- Detect Inefficiencies: Consistent high current consumption suggests inefficient operation, prompting investigation into potential causes like wear and tear or improper settings.
- Optimize Machine Settings: By analysing current trends, operators can fine-tune machine settings to achieve optimal performance while minimizing energy consumption.

Transducer Deployment

The strategic placement of electric transducers within the electrical cabin monoblock provides a comprehensive overview of energy consumption across various critical systems:

- Water Pumps: Monitoring the current absorption of cyclone water pumps allows for optimization of water flow and pressure, minimizing energy waste.
- Crushers: Tracking the current consumption of crusher motors enables operators to identify and address inefficiencies, reducing energy usage.

- Vibrating Screens: Monitoring the current absorption of vibrating screens helps optimize screening efficiency and minimize energy consumption.
- Water Purifier Pump: Tracking the current consumption of the water purifier pump allows for efficient operation and reduced energy usage.

Benefits of Electric Transducers:

- Energy Savings: By identifying and addressing inefficiencies, electric transducers contribute to significant energy savings, reducing operational costs.
- Improved Efficiency: Optimized machine settings and early detection of issues lead to improved overall efficiency and productivity.
- Predictive Maintenance: Monitoring current trends can identify potential problems before they become major issues, reducing downtime and maintenance costs.

Figure 16. Current absorption of the machines in Pioltello plant monitored from MAESTRO's portal.

Figure 17. Annual absorption of the primary crusher 281VE1.

These sensors have been very useful in verifying the correct power absorption within the optimal operating range of individual machinery, directly monitored through the MAESTRO SCADA. These sensors immediately indicate the need for a verification intervention in case of anomalous amperage, preventing unplanned breakdowns and/or production stoppages. This information also gives the measure of the efficiency of the primary and secondary crusher.

2.2.6 Vibration sensors

Vibration sensors, mounted on vibrating screens, act as vigilant guardians, monitoring the screens' motion and providing valuable insights into their performance and health. This data empowers operators to regulate material flow, optimize efficiency, and prevent potential damage.

Vibrating Screens:

Vibrating screens are essential components in many industrial processes, separating materials based on size and weight. Their efficient operation relies on precise and controlled vibrations.

Screen Performance

Vibration sensors, measuring vibrations in three directions (X, Y, and Z), provide a comprehensive understanding of the screen's motion. This data allows operators to:

- Regulate Material Flow: By analysing vibration patterns, operators can adjust the material feed rate to ensure optimal screen performance and prevent overloading.
- Optimize Efficiency: Monitoring vibrations helps identify and address any deviations from the desired operating range, maximizing material separation efficiency.
- Detect Potential Issues: Unexpected changes in vibration patterns, such as increased amplitude or frequency, can indicate potential problems like worn bearings, unbalanced loads, or material clogging.

Benefits of Vibration Sensors:

- Improved Efficiency: Optimized material flow and early detection of issues lead to increased screening efficiency and reduced downtime.
- Predictive Maintenance: Monitoring vibration trends allows for proactive maintenance, preventing catastrophic failures and minimizing downtime.
- Safety Enhancement: Detecting overloading or abnormal vibrations helps prevent potential damage to the screen and ensures a safe working environment.

Figure 18. Vibration sensor installed on the vibrating screen.

The installation of vibration sensors was concentrated on the main Ellivar screen (271VV1) to test its operation and characteristics.

It was thus possible to detect difficulties in interfacing with the plant's SCADA system. It was then decided to take vibration measurements in campaigns to obtain useful data. These campaigns highlighted that the set of vibrations in the operating range of the screen do not constitute a fundamental piece of data for optimal management of the screen itself. More useful information, combined with the previous one related to use and maintenance, is to also combine these sensors with accelerometers that provide more specific information on the operation of the machine.

2.2.7 Cameras

Cameras, strategically positioned throughout the quarry plant, provide a constant visual overview, acting as the eyes of the operator, even as automation advances. This visual monitoring remains crucial for ensuring optimal plant operation and identifying potential issues that may not be detected by sensors alone.

Visual Monitoring

While automation plays a significant role in optimizing plant operations, visual monitoring remains essential for:

- Real-time Observation: Cameras provide a real-time view of critical areas, allowing operators to observe the flow of materials, identify potential blockages, and assess the overall plant condition.

- Identifying Anomalies: Visual inspection can detect anomalies that may not be captured by sensors, such as material spills, equipment malfunctions, or unusual behaviour.
- Ensuring Optimal Parameters: Operators can visually confirm that the plant is running within the desired parameters, ensuring efficient and safe operation.

Strategic Camera Placement

The strategic placement of cameras in key areas, such as the tunnel extraction gates and the conveyor belt feeding the plant, provides a comprehensive view of critical operations:

- Tunnel Extraction Gates: Cameras monitor the extraction process, ensuring smooth material flow and identifying any potential blockages or issues.
- Conveyor Belt: Cameras provide a continuous view of the conveyor belt, allowing operators to monitor material flow, detect any spills or blockages, and assess the overall belt condition.

Benefits of Visual Monitoring:

- Improved Efficiency: Early detection of issues through visual monitoring allows for prompt intervention, minimizing downtime and maximizing plant efficiency.
- Enhanced Safety: Visual observation helps identify potential hazards, ensuring a safe working environment for personnel.
- Decision Support: Visual data provides valuable context for operators, aiding in decision-making and ensuring optimal plant operation.

Figure 19. Video monitoring from quarry operator office (left). Camera installed on the conveyor belt (right).

The installation of cameras and new video monitors in the control room has allowed for better live visualization of the plant's performance, helping the operator in the visual management of the plant and, in combination with the data represented by the SCADA MAESTRO/Data Lake management system, a better overall management of the plant. The intensive use of cameras allows for constant monitoring of even plant processes that are difficult for quarry operators to access, thus contributing to the overall safety of workers. Particular attention must be paid to the positioning and fixing of the cameras on the plant due to the presence of vibrations that could damage the optics. Finally, it is necessary to provide for periodic maintenance and cleaning of the lenses, which are subject to dust, mud, and atmospheric agents.

2.2.8 Level sensors

Level sensors are positioned atop the two silos, monitoring the aggregate levels and ensuring a continuous and uninterrupted supply to the crushers. This precise control optimizes crusher operation, preventing downtime and maximizing efficiency.

Silos

Silos serve as vital storage vessels for aggregates, providing a buffer between the material supply and the crushing process. Maintaining a consistent level within the silos is crucial for smooth and efficient crusher operation.

Monitoring and Controlling Aggregate Levels

Ultrasonic level sensors, mounted on the silos, continuously monitor the aggregate levels, providing real-time data to the control system. This data allows for:

- Automated Crusher Control: When the aggregate level reaches a pre-defined threshold, the control system automatically starts the crusher, ensuring a continuous supply of material.
- Preventing Overloading: As the aggregate level decreases, the control system monitors the level and stops the crusher when it reaches a lower threshold, preventing overloading and ensuring efficient operation.
- Remote Monitoring: The instantaneous level data is remotely monitored, allowing operators to track aggregate levels and intervene if necessary.

Benefits of Level Sensors:

- Continuous Material Supply: By ensuring a consistent aggregate level, level sensors guarantee a continuous supply to the crushers, preventing downtime and maximizing productivity.
- Optimized Crusher Operation: Automated control based on level sensor data optimizes crusher operation, preventing overloading and ensuring efficient material processing.
- Reduced Downtime: Early detection of low aggregate levels allows for timely intervention, minimizing downtime and maximizing plant efficiency.

Figure 20. Silo filling level measured by ultrasonic sensor.

Level sensors are an essential tool for the management and optimization of the plant and for its efficiency, as they contribute to the dosing and delivery of material to the plant sections and regulate the normal workflow of the machinery.

There are no critical issues reported in relation to the ultrasonic sensors positioned inside the silos. The only attention to be paid is to the correct application of the overflow levels by carrying out a correct calibration of the instruments.

2.2.9 Arco weighing system

The installation and implementation of a weigh system at the crushing plant system is a crucial step in developing a comprehensive crushing model. The weigh system, supplied by ARCO, was installed during the week of May 15-19, 2023. It was strategically placed on the conveyor belt immediately after the main cone crusher, coinciding with the location of one of the two PSD sensors. The sensor comprises a triad of idle rollers mounted on a load cell for weight measurement and an idle spring-loaded wheel with an encoder sensor for speed detection.

Data Collection and Transmission:

Initially, data was collected by a dedicated computer and stored locally. Manual data transfer to the Data Lake was implemented in the first phase, involving extraction from the weighing bridge PC and subsequent upload. A dedicated communication system for direct data transmission to the Data Lake was developed and implemented in the second half of 2023. Since January 2024, data is automatically transmitted directly to the Data Lake.

Significance of the Weigh System:

The data collected by the weigh system is essential for the development of MINTEK's crushing model. It provides real-time measurements of the material flow exiting the crusher, offering valuable insights into the crushing process.

The figure below depicts the daily data transmitted to the Data Lake, showcasing the system's effectiveness in monitoring material flow.

Figure 21. Daily production [ton] passing through the ARCO weigh system.

The application of this scale at the exit of the crushing plant has worked correctly throughout the installation period and has been essential for the management of the primary crushing system, working in combination with the MAESTRO Q-vision systems. This type of scale has proven to be reliable in all weather conditions and material quality without encountering any particular critical issues.

2.3 Monitoring sensors and analysis tools + Recognition system for workers (Task 3.3)

The monitoring system installed in both of the wheel loaders in operation provides not only the path and the speed of the machine but the identification in time and place of workers in the surroundings of both mobile machineries.

As described in D3.9 & D3.6, the recognition system for the workers is based on the risk map application developed for this purpose.

The data, once collected by the monitoring system is transferred, analysed and integrated in the reporting system.

Risk map application:

The data collected by the camera system is integrated in the Risk map application (for more information please check D3.6). The integration of the results helps to create an indicator for improving:

1) Road Maintenance:

Proactive road maintenance is crucial for ensuring safety in mining operations. This involves setting up routine inspection schedules, promptly addressing any identified issues, and prioritizing areas with high traffic or a higher risk of deterioration. Partnering with road maintenance specialists and leveraging advanced technologies, such as road condition monitoring systems, can significantly improve maintenance efficiency.

Figure 22. Pothole map

2) Speed Management Strategies:

Effective speed management is essential for reducing risks associated with speeding in mining operations. Key measures include setting and enforcing speed limits, equipping vehicles with speed monitoring devices, and providing comprehensive training for operators on safe driving practices. Regular enforcement and monitoring of speed regulations play a vital role in maintaining a safe work environment.

Figure 23. Speed and distances driven per machinery

3) Personnel Recognition:

The RMA serves as an effective tool for identifying personnel in operational areas. It offers valuable insights into detected individuals, enabling targeted actions through training or best practices (see D3.6). By integrating advanced tools and technologies like the RMA, mining operations can enhance situational awareness and communication, providing real-world examples for training programs that reinforce personnel recognition in operational areas.

Figure 24. Risk Map

Road maintenance, speed control, and personnel recognition are key aspects of health and safety management in mining operations. By prioritizing proactive road upkeep, enforcing speed regulations, and utilizing advanced recognition tools, mining companies can mitigate risks, prevent accidents, and promote a strong safety culture. Collaboration, training, and continuous assessment are essential for ensuring these measures effectively safeguard personnel while optimizing operational efficiency.

This activity has been very useful in identifying the interactions that can occur between moving machines and pedestrians. The study and analysis of the results obtained by identifying the main points of conflict between machines and pedestrians has made it possible to identify the most dangerous situations. As a result, it has been possible to determine a different configuration of the quarry road network, segregating, as much as possible, pedestrian routes from those of heavy traffic. In fact, this application does not constitute an active alarm system, recognizing the human-machine interaction and sending the data to the central detection system without, however, direct feedback.

This technology can be further integrated and developed with an active surveillance system, through fixed cameras mounted on poles, connected to an audible and visual alarm system reported in the control cabin that warn the quarry manager of the presence of a pedestrian in an unauthorized area.

2.4 ICT Platform design implementation (Task 4.2)

The ICT platform in fact is not specific to a given quarry. In D4.2, titled “Report on IQS Design and Architecture,” the design and architecture of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), developed by AKKODIS, are described. The implementation of this architecture and site’s specific development were described in D4.6 “Report on IQS, Services Integration and deployment”. Hence, more details could be found as follow:

- The IQS components currently deployed, their main functions and availability for each pilot site, are described in section 3.1 of D4.3.
- The Centralized data management platform and the CDMF front-end are described in section 3.2 of D4.3.
- Transport service, Plant production service, Environmental data management service, Health and safety service are described in section 3.2.3 of D4.6.
- Business management tools Section 3.4 of D4.6-
- The data lake, the databases, the IoT platform and Talend integration are described respectively in section 3.2.4, 3.2.5, 3.2.6 and 3.2.7 of D4.6-
- The data connectors are described in section 3.3 of D4.6.

The following 3 figures show the front-end welcome page, the Shared data screen and the plant production screen created for Holcim.

Actions	Id	Product Type ↓	Product Name	Date	Production Start	Production End	Down Time
	1	Frantumati	Q/4	18/03/2024	07:33:08	15:02:52	0
	5	Naturali	Q/4	18/03/2024	00:00:00	00:00:00	0
	9	Frantumati	Q/4	03/05/2024	06:57:55	16:57:19	0
	13	Naturali	Q/4	03/05/2024	00:00:00	00:00:00	0
	17	Frantumati	Q/4	18/04/2024	07:19:11	17:00:35	0
	21	Naturali	Q/4	18/04/2024	00:00:00	00:00:00	0
	25	Frantumati	Q/4	24/06/2024	07:10:42	16:58:16	0
	29	Naturali	Q/4	24/06/2024	00:00:00	00:00:00	0
	33	Frantumati	Q/4	17/06/2024	07:45:58	16:54:08	0
	37	Naturali	Q/4	17/06/2024	00:00:00	00:00:00	0

Figure 27. CDMP Front-End – “Plant production” screen.

In Holcim, several quarry processes (Production, Automation, Environment) have been implemented within the IQS, and their data models have been defined. Connections using REST APIs have been created, enabling direct communication for data exchange between the expert systems and the IQS according to a newly defined common data format.

The data integration process has been implemented. Data are flowing at various frequencies (hourly, daily, monthly) depending on the use case. Data integration was achieved using a proxy design pattern adopted by all data providers to push data from Scada system of MAESTRO and PlantSmith system of Roctim to the IQS and to pull data from the IQS by the data consumers. The final result of the IQS data integration within the project across all sites including the data availability status in the data lake is described in section 4 of D4.6.

In addition to the reporting tools provided by the expert systems, the IQS leveraged the Power BI ecosystem to create comprehensive dashboards and reports that provide insights into KPIs from different facets of quarrying. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring. The dashboards are described in section 4.3 of D4.2 and in section 3 of D4.6.

All the dashboards created for Holcim site are accessible in one power-bi application accessible to pilot site’s users as shown in next figure.

Figure 28. DEQ Power BI App for Holcim

2.5 AI algorithms (Task 4.3)

The AI services designed in the project are summarised in the following table mentioning the pilot quarry they belong to:

Table 2. AI Services developed for the different pilots.

AI Service Area	Pilot site	SIGMA	UPM-AI
Hawkeye (CV) COLORIMETRY (QUAL)	CEMEX	X	X
Hawkeye (CV) GRAIN SIZE	CEMEX	X	X
Stock Forecast (CV) STOCKPILE VOLUME	Holcim & Vicat	X	X
Predictive Maintenance (PrMa) - ANOMALIES DETECTION (Acoustic&video&...)	CSI	X	X
Metaquarry (Document Mgt)	Holcim & Vicat	X	
Consumptions & production forecast	CIMPOR	X	X

In this deliverable only the ones pertaining to Holcim Pioltello’s quarry are described.

It is important to mention that in the deliverable D4.3 “Report on the AI Algorithms and Services”, detailed design specifications can be found and the contents that can be found here are in some cases a summary of the text in the deliverable.

2.5.1 Stockpile Volume Calculation

2.5.1.1 General Summary

Table 3. General summary of stockpile volume calculation.

Service Name	Stockpile volume calculation
Overview	<p>The Stockpile volume calculation service aims to integrate visual and data inputs to estimate the volume of the different piles to keep track of the stock available in the quarry. This service is being implemented in Vicat-Fenouillet and HOLCIM-Pioltello quarries in which some stockpiles with different grain sizes are produced. This information and will aid operators and quarry managers in optimizing plant production and multiple other scenarios, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resource Management: Accurate volume monitoring allows quarries to manage their available resources efficiently. It helps keep an up-to-date inventory of the stockpile of materials, ensuring that adequate quantities are available to meet customer demands. ▪ Inventory Control: By tracking stockpile volumes, quarries can avoid overstocking or understocking issues. This translates to reduced waste, optimized stock levels, and cost savings regarding inventory management. ▪ Quality Control: It helps identify potential issues such as material segregation, moisture content variation, and contamination. This early detection aids in maintaining product quality standards. ▪ Safety and Compliance: It's crucial to ensure the safety of workers and adherence to environmental regulations in quarries. Monitoring stockpile volumes helps prevent hazardous overloading situations and compliance with industry regulations. ▪ Predictive Analysis: By continuously monitoring stockpile volumes, quarries can gain insights into the material consumption rate and forecast when a new extraction or shipment will be required. This proactive approach aids in planning and scheduling. <p>A conceptualization of the service is depicted in Figure 65 on actual images from various sites. Subfigures a) and c) illustrate the match between the actual piles in the original photographs and their reconstructed 3D models on two different sites. Subfigure d) provides a heatmap on the top view of the site in b) that matches the colour gradient to piles and terrain height. Finally, e) provides a side view of different piles for a single site, including estimations on their corresponding volumes.</p>

Figure 29. Conceptualization of the service: from visual inputs to volume estimations.

The service calculates the volume of the piles using ground multi-view images obtained through multipoint smartphone data. For this purpose, an APP for smartphones was developed. The service can interpolate volumes, and the output is a single, site-, pile-, and time-referenced numeric value. The historical sequences for a pile or a plant shall describe stock evolution and should be possible to retrieve from the DEQ information system.

The required precision on the stockpiles is above 95% in volume. This requirement was validated during discussions with the different sites involved in the DEQ project while defining the service and the performance level required. The acquired data encompass geo-referenced visual input(s).

A short guideline to collect smartphone video footage using two APPs (Sensor Logger (Google, 2023), and Open Camera (Google, 2023)) was developed. These allowed tests on the reconstruction of the piles using controlled video acquisition conditions and rough GPS data (Open Camera) and to incorporate pose information to speed up the reconstruction process from sensor data (Sensor Logger). Nevertheless, scarce GPS and video footage should be enough for pile reconstruction, though much is gained when additional data is available. For this reason, the service was designed to handle diverse data sources.

Key Components

- Smartphone (or drone data, or satellite, or multi-camera): to collect the georeferenced video footage around the piles.
 - Communications: The smartphone app must upload the video footage to the cloud for processing. Optimisations may mitigate data exchange running on an Internet connection. Video data can be flushed whenever the quarry operator asks. Additional configurations can restrict data uploading.
 - Back-end servers: Incorporate an API to operate, manage users and data, and upload video footage. The latter is processed by the AI modules.
 - Data storage and processing: The massive video footage must be uploaded and processed. Due to the size of the video data, the service preserves this information for a limited amount of time. The results and pieces of evidence of the volume computation are significantly less demanding.
 - AI implementation: It is integrated into the back-end servers, including GPU acceleration. The current version of the solution includes trained models that could operate without further training.
- A general Architecture diagram is appended:

	<p><i>Figure 30. General Architecture for the Stockpile Volume Calculation service.</i></p> <p>Only service outputs, from the data lake to the dashboards and other services, are served to the IQS infrastructures.</p> <p>The solution is intended for the quarry management teams. Quarry managers can collect evidence on producing and storing materials of different qualities and piles. Business managers have direct access to production information.</p> <p>Additionally, the service is intended for other audiences, including those acquiring raw materials and project managers using these materials.</p> <p>Furthermore, the technology developed for this service focuses on digitalising 3D structures. Such capabilities can also be used in other businesses involved in data digitalisation.</p>
<p>Target Audience</p>	<p>The solution is intended for the quarry management teams. Quarry managers can collect evidence on producing and storing materials of different qualities and piles. Business managers have direct access to production information.</p> <p>Additionally, the service is intended for other audiences, including those acquiring raw materials and project managers using these materials.</p> <p>Furthermore, the technology developed for this service focuses on digitalising 3D structures. Such capabilities can also be used in other businesses involved in data digitalisation.</p>
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>Smartphone (currently only Android is supported).</p> <p>Alternatively, the AI system supports other georeferenced video and multi-view images, including drone flights and satellites.</p> <p>For rapid processing, the back-end service must be powered by a GPU. This component accelerates the processing of video frames and expedites the volume computation process. Without acceleration, the processing time increases to 20x, delaying output delivery. The GPU must be integrated into the back-end.</p>
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>No installation is required at the quarry site.</p> <p>The solution requires deploying a full backend that incorporates all capabilities, including user management, data processing, and data exchange with the IQS infrastructures, which include DEQ Data Lake and Data Warehouse. The backend operates as a cloud infrastructure.</p>

Communication Protocols -	5G or Wi-Fi. Wi-Fi connection on the smartphone data may be preferred for uploading video footage due to the amount of data involved. Several different videos can be uploaded after they have been collected. They remain on the operator's smartphone, labelled pending in the APP.
Data Storage & Management	Data is stored on operators' smartphones and backend servers. The latter is currently operating as a cloud solution for the service but is installed on UPM premises. We have tested several cloud solutions and found no restrictions for future deployments after the project is completed. Results are served to the IQS infrastructure for storage, backup, etc.
AI Integration & Implementation	We use AI capabilities to process video footage, digitalize the stockpiles, and compute the volumes. AI models provide computer vision capabilities, segmentation, illumination and location correction, enhanced multiview matching, as well as optimized 3D computation, and shape correction.
Application Features	<p>The service can build a <u>complete 3D model from georeferenced video</u> footage or image sequences. This can be collected using smartphones or other unmanned vehicles. Despite the limitations and spurious effects of smartphone GPS data and video quality, the models are successfully produced. The depth and resolution of 3D models may be adjusted for different applications. For this particular service on stockpile volume calculation, low-density meshed models are preferred to expedite the volume calculation.</p> <p>This service has three <u>user interfaces</u>.</p> <p>The APP is the main interface for interacting with the collected data, the evidence, and the results obtained on the stockpile volume. We have implemented two different APPS:</p> <p>The data acquisition APP is used as a measuring solution to run tests and demonstrate the functionalities. This APP should no longer be needed as these functionalities will be included in the following ones.</p> <p>The user APP. This included extended capabilities to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create new accounts Recover the user password and set access credentials <p>APP full navigation, including historical data, video footage collection, results presentation, user profile and management.</p> <p>Receiving notifications: new tasks, new videos to process, new processing completed with new results.</p> <p>The complementary Web version of the APP is to be completed to ease interaction and provide a complete service experience: full registration, access to reports, export data, invoicing, etc.</p> <p>The service's dashboard provides access to the detailed information uploaded to the Data Lake and the Data Warehouse. The PowerBI dashboard only provides a summary of the results obtained.</p>
Security & Compliance	<p>The app uses token-based authentication for secure user identification. A single sign-on approach has been implemented, which may also be used on the web-based interface. We used Google's Firebase Firestore NoSQL database and Firestore Authentication. Tests were conducted on a free account, including user and data management.</p> <p>Furthermore, the APP defines different roles associated with different privileges. The list of roles includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ADMIN (for the account/company manager) with unrestricted access and additional access requirements: two-factor authentication.

	<p>MANAGER (for the quarry manager) has no control over the company account, is designated by the ADMIN, can generate lower-level profiles, define tasks, and assign them.</p> <p>OPERATOR (for quarry operators) manages the data acquisition process on their own or in response to a task assigned by a MANAGER.</p> <p>TEST USER (newbies): Any user can download the app and learn more about it. However, those who request a demo will get a code to unveil the app's demo functionalities. Demo features are restricted from the cloud side and can include all role levels if this is approved.</p> <p>None of the information required for this service is related to the GDPR. Nevertheless, no user information, including contact details, is stored in the APP or the system.</p> <p>No specific security measures have been placed on the APP-collected data, as this is regarded as non-critical information. Videos are not encrypted nor protected in any specific way within the user's smartphone.</p> <p>Data exchange uses HTTPS-protected connections on the APIs to preserve privacy on the unchanged data, particularly any user-specific information that is exchanged, including user and service tokens.</p>
<p>Performance Metrics</p>	<p><u>System up-time</u> (on the server side): intended for 24/7. In practice, the Service Level Agreement (SLA) should cover up to 95% of up-time.</p> <p><u>Accuracy in volume estimation</u>: Discussions within the DEQ workforce suggest a minimum accuracy of 95% for a valuable solution. Tests conducted at this point were above 98% accuracy. Compared with other solutions available on the market, the accuracy level is the same as obtained by trained technicians and drone-flight data.</p> <p><u>Data processing speed</u> (per MB of video footage): A full file video (5 minutes to process) currently requires less than 10 minutes. In optimistic scenarios (high-quality footage), it goes down to 5 minutes (1:1). For low-quality footage, processing time increases (up to 1:2).</p> <p><u>Number of monthly active users</u> (MAUs): A larger number of users is key to lead generation and increased service use. We intend to track the number of visits to the service, the recursive use of the volume estimation feature, and historical data consultation and exporting. These metrics can be computed but will not be tracked until the Android app version is published and open to the market.</p> <p><u>Versatility</u>. The solution is device-agnostic. For the time being, only an Android version of the app is available. If possible, an iOS version will be developed to cover 90%+ of the smartphone market, particularly for managers and top levels.</p> <p><u>Replicability</u>. The solution can be replicated on all five continents, regardless of the applications and quarry. Tests conducted showed that stockpiles made of other materials may as well be evaluated.</p>
<p>Support & Maintenance</p>	<p>The app incorporates support and contact functionalities. During tests, no messages were communicated directly from the latest versions of the app.</p> <p>Technical support was provided through direct contact with the UPM-AI team during DEQ. In the future, this will be entirely managed through the APP.</p> <p>The service can be updated from the Android OS, the app, and the Cloud Backend. The latter connects to the app and can verify the running version of the up-to-run seamless updates with minimum user intervention. Android notifications can also suggest full app updates, as they are typically handled.</p> <p>Regular software patches need to be provided to address bugs and vulnerabilities.</p>

<p>Business Model & Pricing</p>	<p>We have developed a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) model for this service. The model is based on competitors providing similar services, though these services provide very different performance levels and features.</p> <p>The market analysis suggests we focus on early adopters among large enterprises following the DEQ project. The new stages focus on client funding and avoiding equity sharing. Organic growth on the B2B side is considered possible, while individual agents and small and medium enterprises should come in the meantime, provided that specific pricing is provided to target them.</p> <p>The estimated TAM of the mining industry worldwide may reach 2.3 billion dollars (1.0 billion dollars in the EU). SAM focuses on the 10% of companies that have expressed interest in tech solutions to this need, reaching 10,0 M dollars in the EU. Starting from DEQ, SOM could easily reach 20% of this for 2M dollars a year.</p> <p>Customer segments: The service is aimed at quarrying sites or other industrial environments that require production or storage monitoring, such as farming industries, transport, etc.</p> <p>Value proposition: The innovation measures the volume of the piles of stored materials or products and provides and estimation of the volume. For countable items, it may be adjusted to provide a number of it.</p> <p>Channels: Lead generation from UPM contacts in specialised forums and contacts from associations and workgroups, including those headed by ANEFA. Direct sales via interviews of commercial teams with IT departments. Use Sigma’s web channel and commercial offices in Madrid, London and Miami.</p> <p>Customer relationships: Personalized assistance fitting customers’ needs for LEs and SMEs. The APP is meant to serve as a hub for fostering stronger customer relationships and driving engagement. It leverages user experience and support to provide data analytics and enhance the user experience. It facilitates digital scale economies by allowing businesses to reach a broader customer base without the need for physical expansion. It offers features like targeted marketing tools, user behaviour insights, and automated communication channels, enabling personalized experiences to be monitored and evaluated.</p> <p>To boost engagement, it incorporates a user-friendly interface with intuitive navigation, real-time notifications and updates, knowledge sharing among users, and space to include other features, such as news, blogs on use, reviews of the product, and information on coming releases and how to use them.</p> <p>The app aims to become an indispensable tool for measuring stock by serving as a central platform for customer interactions and growth opportunities. It streamlines digitalization processes, ultimately contributing to increased efficiency across the market.</p> <p>Revenue streams: An annual subscription fee, depending on the number of operators, plus pay-per-use as the video footage is processed.</p> <p>Key resources: We avoid the need for field installers or HW specialists. Only IT personnel are needed. Computation resources include cloud storage and servers for data processing.</p> <p>Key activities: Monitoring, data analysis, process improvement.</p> <p>Key partners: Customers and end users, including associations.</p> <p>Cost structure: Human resources for development, O&M resources, servers (storage and processing), and marketing resources.</p> <p>The pricing model is based on two trenches:</p>
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	<p>An <u>annual subscription</u> fee is charged to access the service, launch the account and configuration, and keep generated data throughout the years. This fee varies depending on the number of quarry sites, operators involved, and service processing speed. It may be around 1.000 – 2.000 EUR per site for consecutive years, incremented by +1.000 EUR in the first year for the setup, and in consecutive years only if specific upgrading or adaptations are required.</p> <p>A <u>pay-per-use model</u> for the stockpile volume calculation each time a video is processed. To ease this process, charging runs on the size of the uploaded video footage (megabytes of data). Final prices are to be defined after segmentation. Tentative numbers suggest these may be between 0.5 and 2.0 EUR per MB.</p> <p>Additionally, initial analyses suggest a PoC (Proof of Concept) pricing with no pay-per-use, as well as different plans, including DEMO and Freemium access. These and others may be used as tools for lead generation and other marketing strategies.</p> <p>The model's pricing will NOT include initial requirement analysis or deployment fees. O&M will be included in the annual subscription.</p>
<p>Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>For years, the lack of digitalisation of production data was the leading competitor for such a service. Some alternatives have been used in recent years, but the number of alternatives is still quite limited.</p> <p>In mining, 80% are independent contractors with drones and hand-made reports. None of these provide continuous monitoring SaaS capabilities. Continuous monitoring is a costly handmade process involving digital tools that are relatively slow and typically require stopping operations.</p> <p>In the Computer Vision space, alternatives include companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SR Measures (South Africa, 2012) uses deep learning, is multipoint, and focuses on individual piles. Its granted accuracy sits at 70%. - Moesure (UK, 2014) is the first motion-based measuring tool that utilises high-performance inertial sensors packed into a handheld device. Products currently use smartphone technology to accelerate measurements. - Trimble Access (Dubai, 2017). It uses specific HW instrumentation to collect the data and provide volume estimations. These components require proficient operators and long learning curves. - ITS Geo Solutions (Germany, 2022). Multifaceted reconstruction. Dense pointclouds construction. Clean input was collected in good capturing conditions. It requires trained operators and is under a costly subscription. <p>The developed AI service can directly operate with georeferenced data from smartphone video. The solution is device-agnostic and could be extended to other devices. The system can run 24/7, with an estimated precision of over 98% accuracy, from small piles (less than 1 cubic meter) to real large ones (several thousand). This represents a relative +25% improvement in reported accuracy while handling complex acquisition conditions. Tests conducted in DEQ suggest that inexperienced operators could easily manage the APP and that the learning curve to collect quality video footage is very rapid.</p>
<p>Future Enhancements</p>	<p>A complete user experience requires a web structure that matches the APP structure and dashboard presentation capabilities directly connected to this. For such a service to operate, we need presentation capabilities similar to those provided by the PowerBI dashboards in DEQ. A similar structure can be developed using external (cloud or in-premise) services.</p> <p>Ongoing upgrades:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Video data selection software will be integrated into the app. This capability should reduce the amount of data that needs to be exchanged. Preliminary tests are being conducted to evaluate this possibility. For example, frames providing purely redundant information could be removed. - We aim to enhance visualisations with evidence of the computed volumes, specifically on the video input and the 3D meshes that reproduce the stockpiles. The models should be reduced. To reduce storage, we may use 2D visualisations instead of full meshes. - As an extension to this evidence, generating automatic reports may be a relevant feature for many sites. Complete extension reports have been the standard output delivered to them after stockpiles are assessed. This tool may expedite the acquisition of the technology. <p>Backlog (to be evaluated):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During video acquisition, it is technically possible to run automatic data selection on the video stream. This requires specialised AI models to select relevant data for 3D reconstruction. - During video acquisition, one may like to enhance the experience of the pile recording. A completion bar based on geolocation may help operators validate the acquired data right while they are collecting the video footage. - It is possible to enrich the collected data with information about the camera's tilt and pan for programmed tasks and based on the operator's geolocation during acquisition. Preliminary tests suggest that this information expedites the volume computation process and reduces noise. - With location information and orientation referring to the operators, models can predict the operator's trajectory and restrict the line of sight for piles already identified in a given task. - We used a standard dockerised implementation on the backend servers to handle model reconstruction. Parallel processing should be achieved through a dynamically managed parameter server architecture that automatically scaled worker nodes using Kubernetes orchestration. This system would employ chain replication with relaxed consistency guarantees to maintain continuity during server failures, allowing backup parameter servers to resume operations with warm in-memory weights while preserving high GPU utilisation during downtimes. - For resource management, we aim to implement automated server lifecycle controls using CLI-based triggers to scale GPU-accelerated instances based on real-time compute demands. This will allow us to achieve significant throughput improvements.
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2.5.1.2 Activities performed since November 2023

During this time, we completed numerous milestones towards the final service productization. The elementary capabilities required for volume computation (at prototype level, outside the laboratory) had already been validated in the previous period. In this one, we focused on building the product from the user side (data acquisition APP and results presentation) to the server (back-office) side.

Validated integrated APP: geo-referenced video on a single APP

During this period, we collaborated with the quarry sites, collecting video footage on stockpiles using two different data collection APPs and evaluating the results obtained. New video footage was collected at Vicat Fenouillet's quarry site. The video footage collected, and the results obtained were validated by all teams involved. The level of precision was found to be sufficient, as well as the details offered. From this point on, activities focused on building a fully operative prototype of the service, integrating the full APP experience and required backend.

User-oriented APP version

To proceed to the user's final design of the service app, it is essential to identify the requirements, objectives and needs a user may experience. For this, we defined eight use cases and five user stories epics. User stories, from the perspective

of those who might use the system, describe what they want to achieve and the benefits they expect to obtain. On the other hand, use cases adopt a more technical perspective, detailing specific event flows and interactions between the user and the system. The combination of user stories and use cases offers a complete understanding of the project requirements, from user needs to the technical operation of the system.

The use cases and user stories included below are not limited to presenting and visualising results but cover most parts of the service. The goal was not to overlook any aspect of users' needs and interests in the service.

Hereafter, we include a reduced analysis of the key epics identified:

Epic 1: User Account Management.

Story 1.1: As a user, I want to create an account to be able to log in

Description: The user wants to create a new account to access the application and use its features.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The user can access a registration form.
- The user can enter their data (name, email, password, etc.).
- The user can create the account and access the application once registration is complete.

Story 1.2: Exploration. As a user, I want to change the language to understand what's in the application.

Description: The user wants to change the language of the application interface to their preferred language.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers an option to select the interface language.
- The user can choose from a list of available languages.
- The application interface is displayed in the language selected by the user.

Story 1.3: As a user, I want to log in to use the application with my data

Description: The user wants to log into the application using their username and password.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The user can access a login form.
- The user can enter their username and password.
- The application validates the user's credentials.
- The user logs into the application and accesses its functionalities.

Story 1.4: As a user, I want to be able to reset my password in case I forget it

Description: The user wants to recover their password if they have forgotten it.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers an option to recover the password.
- The user can enter the email address associated with the account.
- The application sends an email to the user with a link to reset the password.
- The user can access the link and set a new password.

Story 1.5: As a user, I want to access my profile to view my data

Description: The user wants to access their profile to view their data.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The user can access a profile section within the application.
- The user's profile displays their personal data (name, email, etc.).

Story 1.6: As a user, I want to modify my profile to keep the data updated

Description: The user wants to modify their personal data in their profile.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The user can access a profile editing section within the application.
- The user can modify their personal data (name, email, etc.).
- The application validates the new data entered by the user.
- The user's personal data is correctly updated in their profile.

Epic 2: Video Management

Story 2.1: As a user, I want to be able to record videos for the data to be analysed with artificial intelligence

Description: The user wants to record a video within the application and have it analysed using artificial intelligence.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers a video recording function.
- The user can focus on the camera and record a video.
- The recorded video is stored in the application or sent to a server for analysis.
- Artificial intelligence analyses the video and generates relevant data.
- The user can access the analysed video data.

Story 2.2: As an operator user, I want to see the status of the videos I have made.

Description: The operator user wants to view the status of the videos they have recorded or uploaded to the platform.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application displays a list of videos with their current status (recorded, in analysis, analysis completed, error).
- The operator user can select a video to view its status in detail.
- The operator user can view the analysed data of the video if the analysis has finished.

Epic 3: Data Analysis

Story 3.1: As a manager user, I want to be able to view the analysed data of the quarry

Description: The manager user wants to view the data analysed from the videos recorded by the quarry users.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers a section to view the data analysed by the quarry.
- The manager user can view the data based on the desired stack or individual recordings.
- The manager user can view the analysed data as graphs.

Story 3.2: As an admin user, I want to be able to view the data analysed by the group or company.

Description: The administrator user wants to view the analysed data of the videos recorded by all users of the group or company.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers a section to view analysed data of the group or company.
- The administrator user can view the data based on the desired stack or quarry or individual recordings.
- The administrator user can view the analysed data as graphs.

Epic 4: User Account Management

Story 4.1: As an admin or manager user, I want to be able to manage my subordinates' accounts to expel them, assign work, or change their access level.

Description: The administrator or manager user wants to manage the accounts of their subordinates within the application.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application offers a section to manage subordinate accounts.
- The administrator or manager user can view a list of their subordinates and their associated data.
- The administrator or manager user can expel a subordinate from the application.
- The administrator or manager user can assign work to a subordinate.
- The administrator or manager user can change the access level of a subordinate (user, operator, manager, admin).

Story 4.2: As a user, I want to be able to view the work assigned to me

Description: The user wants to view the work assigned to them by an administrator or manager.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application displays a section of tasks assigned to the user.
- The user can see the description of each task, its deadline, and its status (pending, completed).
- The user can mark a task as completed once they have finished it.

Epic5: Error Handling

Story 5.1: As a user, I want to see what has caused an error to know what to do

Description: The user wants to receive clear and helpful information in case an error occurs in the application.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application displays a descriptive error message indicating the cause of the error.
- The error message offers the user a solution or steps to resolve the problem.
- The application logs the error for analysis by developers.

Story 5.2: As a user, I want to be able to contact support to receive help if I can't resolve the error myself.

Description: The user wants to be able to contact the application's support team if they cannot resolve an error on their own or have a particular request.

Acceptance Criteria:

- The application provides an email address to contact technical support (inactive in this Final Project).
- The user can send an email.

- The support team assists the user in resolving the error.

We chose to build a React Native application using the Expo framework. The latter is ideal for developers seeking a more straightforward and faster setup, as it offers a wide range of integrated tools and supports standard features without additional configuration.

Figure 31. Class structure for the APP

We tested Firebase (Google Service from Ireland, EU) for rapid testing and validation of the development platform. All these tests will also be reproduced on other platforms and deployed within EU infrastructures. Firebase offers various backend services, such as authentication tools, real-time databases, cloud storage, and notification management. We evaluated the ease of use, access to real-time databases, existing support and documentation, and scalability. Our benchmark included AWS Amplify, Microsoft Azure, and Backendless. The class diagram that was implemented is elementary yet illustrative enough and is depicted in Figure 1.

The current version of this app includes up to nine different views, including those for user signup, login, and registration; information and data visualisations (up to 4 different views), including side information on the DEQ project; and views for data acquisition, user profiles, and account management. Figure 2 summarizes some of the most illustrative views.

The designed APP includes notification capabilities. These could be integrated with the Google Android notification system, but we kept them separate inside the APP for better control of the visualisation.

Figure 32. Visualization on the Use APP deployed. Some of the key views are depicted, including the login, workload management, task registration, and stock details.

The development of the front for this APP was partially funded by Ayuntamiento de Madrid and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, within the Program for “FOMENTO DE LA INNOVACIÓN A TRAVÉS DE PROGRAMAS DE INCUBACIÓN, ACELERACIÓN O ESCALADO DE PROYECTOS INNOVADORES DESARROLLADOS POR UNIVERSIDADES PÚBLICAS, FUNDACIONES SIN ÁNIMO DE LUCRO VINCULADAS A UNIVERSIDADES PÚBLICAS, PARQUES CIENTÍFICOS Y ORGANISMOS PÚBLICOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN” (Promotion Of Innovation Through Incubation, Acceleration, Or Scaling Programs For Innovative Projects Developed By Public Universities, Non-Profit Foundations Linked To Public Universities, Science Parks, And Public Research Organizations). This was awarded in May 2024, with a 3,550 EUR budget dedicated to the activities described above as part of the entrepreneurial project acoplA.

Video footage defects: analysis and correction

Sun and lens flares, light reflections, and refraction contribute to the aesthetic appeal of visual assets and set the general atmosphere, providing an artistic and dramatic element. Flares and reflections are due to a luminous source and a lens arranged at specific angles relative to the centre of the camera lens and the CCD sensor. Contrarily, diffraction appears due to a partial obstruction or a change in light propagation. Despite their visual appeal and aesthetic value, which drove early attempts to generate them artificially, these effects substantially challenge open-world data acquisition for engineering applications.

It is well-documented that significant alterations in lighting conditions profoundly impact the performance of computer vision applications. The challenge is particularly relevant when cameras cannot be positioned or adjusted due to their fixed locations or to maintain a specific viewpoint. The complexity is heightened when multiple images or video sequences are involved. The need for fixed acquisition conditions clashes with the desire to capture diverse visual perspectives, requiring innovative solutions to address flares, diffraction, and reflections.

Figure 33. The overall scheme for the proposed pipeline (central block, yellow background) and the OpenSfm processing pipeline (right block, white background) includes some examples of the processing's intermediate results.

SfM (structure-from-motion) reconstructs three-dimensional structures from a sequence of two-dimensional images or frames collected from different viewpoints. As a result, the algorithm computes estimates on the 3D geometry and camera poses and tracks. When collecting the input sequence, the latter two correspond to a moving camera's location and orientation relative to the reconstructed geometry. Input images may be discarded when the algorithm is unsuccessful in finding a match with the provided sequence. The resulting geometry and camera poses may be incomplete when the algorithm cannot find a suitable transformation, causing holes or breaks in the reconstructed 3D geometry and invalidating any posterior computation on the pile's volume.

To grasp an idea of the time required to process a video and the distribution of time along the pipeline blocks, we computed these values for a standard 440 MB MP4 footage of 175 seconds and 1920x1080 pixels per frame from our dataset with OpenSfm SIFT-GPU branch, running on a GPU-accelerated i9-9900K 64 GB CPU using a 16 GB Geforce RTX4060Ti. The percentage of time devoted to each stage is included to the right in the Figure below alongside the corresponding block. OpenSfm devotes most of its time to compute the pointclouds, mainly to the final output depth maps and only a little to the initial, low-resolution reconstruction. Once a preliminary match is achieved based on anchor points, producing the actual models optimising the reconstruction and the camera points requires a costly procedure. The better the key points match, the easier and quicker the optimisation.

Figure 34. The proposed pipeline achieves inputs (top) and outputs (bottom) in different configurations: without any preprocessing (left), with early masking (centre), and using the refined masked (right).

To validate our hypotheses and the results of our work, we conducted several experiments following the structure of the proposed pipeline. On different setups and different input data, we computed the following figures on a synthetic (with and without distortions) and a real dataset: (i) the number of successfully matched points in the SfM reconstruction on each video, (ii) the number of reconstructed point clouds and the average confidence level assigned to the reconstructed points, (iii) the percentage of reconstruction achieved.

We integrated additional Computer Vision models specifically trained to match quarry and challenging illumination conditions for this task. The original flare models had to be entirely retrained, and the data augmentation reworked to represent actual real-world conditions and produce meaningful results.

The intermediate and final outputs of the proposed pipeline for a sample frame are illustrated in the top row of the following Figure. In a standard configuration where the proposed pipeline is unavailable, the input frame (top image) will be the visual input to the OpenSfm. Conversely, this frame and the computed mask are used as inputs for the OpenSfm on the proposed model. The masked input frame from the example below is included as an example.

We also evaluated the difference in the SfM reconstruction from the distorted videos using the synthetic and real-world datasets to compare the original reconstruction results and the improvements introduced by the proposed preprocessing of the video sequences. We include snapshots of the reconstructed geometries without the proposed pipeline (left) and include the proposed masking (centre) and refined methods (right). The top row exemplifies the inputs to the OpenSfm on each configuration. At the bottom of the figure, the first row depicts views of the reconstructions achieved, and the second illustrates the camera tracks. The red dots correspond to these tracks, while the green ones represent GPS positions assigned to the frames while capturing the video.

Certainly, SfM reconstructions on the unprocessed video sequences are improved when using the pre-processed sequences and masks. While the original reconstructions were fed with 17% of the video frames, 2.5% of them were rejected during the reconstruction. Those frames did not include matches and could not contribute to the reconstruction. The outcome included large unreconstructed regions (21%) and significant holes. Contrarily, the preprocessing pipeline was able to select the frames appropriately, slightly increasing the number of those processed (additional 3%) while achieving an 87% with the first method proposed, involving the masks and the varying sample, and up to 99%+ for the final, refined algorithm across all the videos in our datasets.

Synthetic dataset design and implementation

We found that the current state of the art in 3D reconstruction in conditions matching quarry sites lacked a dataset for benchmarking. This is a critical problem while aiming to validate the results obtained outside the actual physical outdoor measures. Due to this limitation, we designed, implemented, and produced a synthetic dataset to be publicly shared to evaluate new solutions and future enhancements.

We generated three synthetic video sequences to qualify and quantify the impact of the effects evaluated in this contribution under controlled conditions. We built a synthetic model of a digitised pile, set it in a computed-generated outdoor daylight scenario and rendered a video while moving the camera around this pile as if the scene had been recorded using a smartphone. We also introduced the light effects observed in the previous dataset, which we had been discussing throughout this contribution. A second video was produced, including a punctual light source imitating the sun without the effects. Finally, a third video was rendered using diffuse light. The lower row of the Figure 5 includes snapshots of the rendered videos showcasing the different effects. These effects match actual conditions found on the video footage collected in the DEQ tests that were conducted, see upper row.

For this activity, we used our trained AI models for flare and glare generation and addition, which we ran on top of a generated Blender 4.2 LTS project. In this project, we defined the space for the pile, as well as the geometry and structure of the surroundings, to simulate real data acquisition conditions. These included the relative location of the sun. The software allowed us to simulate the moving operator handling the smartphone while recording the video footage. The scenario that was designed could be used in the future on other digitalized piles to validate the reconstruction and assessment process.

The dataset publication is pending as of the day this report was written. This will be publicly released as part of a contribution submitted to an international conference.

Figure 35. Snapshots of images containing the addressed visual effects.

Full processing pipeline

For estimating material stockpile volumes (or other objects), we follow a modular pipeline consisting of three main stages:

- *Preprocessing*: From a video capturing the stockpile (ideally encircling it completely), we execute:
 - Frame extraction: Decompose video into frames containing (or later enriched with) metadata about the capture device's position, orientation, and timestamp.
 - Intelligent frame selection: Optimize computational efficiency by selecting only frames with significant visual variance, as consecutive frames often provide redundant information.
 - Masking: Remove irrelevant regions from frames that don't contribute to reconstruction.
 - Flare and glare removal: Mitigate sun glare artefacts that significantly distort mound reconstruction accuracy.
 - Metadata handling: Add external metadata to frames if not embedded during capture.
- *Reconstruction*: Uses SfM algorithms:
 - Input: Pre-processed frames with the highest reconstruction relevance.
 - Output: Noisy 3D point cloud of the reconstructed stockpile/object.
- *Postprocessing*
 - Filtering: To remove outliers. Signal processing techniques achieve significant noise reduction.
 - Meshing: Convert filtered point cloud into a triangular mesh with vertices at reconstructed points.
 - Volume estimation: Calculate stockpile volume using the tetrahedron method from triangular mesh.

Several stages of this pipeline require GPU acceleration on the AI models. These include the intelligent frame selection, the masking, flare and glare removal, and the output denoising.

The entire processing pipeline for the video footage is illustrated in Figure 36. The referred metadata includes georeferencing, relative orientation, and position information to ease 3D reconstruction.

Figure 36. The complete processing pipeline for volume estimation.

We start from the video input, process the video sequences, and incorporate geolocation and other metadata. The following stages match the previous description of the pipeline.

Development of back-end capabilities

The back-end system consists of various interconnected modules that communicate with each other. This section will present a general architecture with all the modules. To understand the configuration of the individual modules, it is also necessary to understand their function within the system and their interconnection with other modules.

Figure 37. Summary of the infrastructure of the dockerised back-end service.

Figure 37 connects the different modules of the general architecture and their connections. Not all modules will be developed in this work, but all are important to understand the system's operation. The modules involved are:

- Service API: Python server for endpoint deployment. Very common for network deployments.
- Queue Manager: request orchestrator for queries and results. We used RabbitMQ.
- Artificial Intelligence: We used a module dedicated to calculating volumes from videos. We used an extended implementation of the OpenSfM, including the capabilities listed before.
- NoSQL Database focuses on monitoring the different processes. We used Loki + Prometheus.
- Visualisation Interface: This is used to monitor and manage requests visually. We used Grafana.
- SQL Database: This module is dedicated to responding to received requests. They must be separated from the traffic because they can arrive asynchronously to the queries.

To manage and monitor the deployment, we included Traefik to monitor the framework's overall status.

Business model formalisation

We developed and validated an entire service business model with the help of two world-class investors in this space. This activity was conducted within a Training Program for entrepreneurs organised by UPM.

Based on this service's unique features, we found a substantial opportunity (numbers in this document) and ran several simulations on cash flow and profitability under different scenarios. Results show that the proposed business model may cover the existing market needs well and identify that materials buyers and contractors developing the projects using them may share this need. These are all three faces of the same activity, and all need to control the amount of available material at an affordable and controlled price.

Moreover, companies outside the raw materials sector expressed interest during the DEQ dissemination activities. Specifically in the mining sector, where silos may be used at some point but not continuously along the value chain. In other industries, factories store the resources necessary for production in piles of different shapes and sizes. This includes food and paper production industries.

The business model was presented to the 2024 Edition of ActúaUPM Competition under the initiative for entrepreneurship acopia. This was awarded the Top Rank project (15,000 EUR, December 2024). Previously, in this very

competition, the same initiative was awarded as one of the 10 top ideas for innovation in UPM (granted 1,000 EUR, June 2024).

News: <https://www.upm.es/?id=CON16159&prefmt=articulo&fmt=detail>

The accompanying figure illustrates the project's one-page summary, which includes full information about the project and the completed business model.

2.5.2 MetaQuarry

2.5.2.1 General Summary

The following table summarises the main features of the MetaQuarry service that was designed for Holcim. The latter enhancements are included. The detailed specification and design can be found in D4.3 “Report on the AI Algorithms and Services”.

Table 4. General summary of MetaQuarry services

Section	Description
Service Name	METAQUARRY SERVICE
Overview	<p>Quarries handle lots of documentation that is stored safely. This documentation is very diverse: contracts, administrative accounting, invoices, regulations, HR documents and a big etc. What is true, however, is that they do not produce a lot of documentation in terms of manual editing; in many cases it is still produced by hand and, subsequently digitalized. It was discovered that quarries were very interested in having advanced search capabilities in several languages to trace all sorts of information stored, in many cases, in very complex directory and server directory trees. Also, the possibility of getting summaries from the Natural language processing tool proposed by Sigma will enable their easier finding of, for instance, instructions for repairs in machine manuals, contact information for different suppliers or the date and a summary of given works being performed in the quarry by third parties.</p> <p>These tools that have been integrated into MetaQuarry will bring together in a federated way (depending on the Databases organization of the quarry information) sources of information of any nature accessible through an API and allow searches and retrieval of information from natural language queries to locate fragments and contents of interest (regulations, manuals, contracts, tutorial videos, etc.). Therefore, it was proposed that DEQ develop a system that complements the management of digital files, making use of different AI processing techniques based on NLP.</p> <p>Quarry organizations have digital files in different media (documents with text and images, videos, audios, web pages, databases, social networks, etc.) in either native or compressed formats, located in various repositories, which greatly complicates the task of searching their content without the appropriate tools. Therefore, a significant part of the company's documentation base remains hidden for consultation, analysis and exploitation tasks.</p> <p>To overcome this limitation, Sigma proposed to develop MetaQuarry a solution that will reuse the available digital repositories and will allow content to be retrieved through searches expressed in natural language and which explore any type of document previously indexed through the search engine that it incorporates. To this end, MetaQuarry is able to handle and search documents stored in different commercial or open-source cloud or private storage.</p> <p>Basically, MetaQuarry is a RAG-type (Generation Augmented Recovery) system, that combines search and language generation functionalities through LLMs (Large Language Models). On the one hand, it retrieves relevant documents, and on the other, it finds suitable answers inside these documents.</p> <p>For testing purposes in HOLCIM, a private cloud was customized for HOLCIM so that they could upload any documentation they considered of interest to use for evaluation purpose.</p>
Key Components	A general Architecture diagram is appended:

Figure 38. Component architecture

It is important to highlight that the components are basically running on SIGMA servers for the project's evaluation and implementation phases. The tool itself can be deployed locally if the need arises following, for example, security criteria. For HOLCIM, a cloud approach was adopted. The description of the different components is outlined here (Contents extracted from D4.3).

Web Application

The MetaQuarry web application is based on Python's Streamlit Framework and integrates with a search engine described below.

Streamlit has some features that make it of great interest for such a project. It is a framework very much oriented to the field of AI data visualization and is used as a standard solution in similar solutions by the AI community.

The main functionalities of the Web Application are:

- **Authentication.** It is the initial component that allows authenticated access and cookie management natively. Authentication guarantees the security of potentially confidential information.
- **Questions:** It offers a text window in which users can write a query or question. When sending a query, the system will return a list of documents in order of relevance to the query and, whenever possible, an automated answer to the question asked, obtained by means of an LLM (Large Language Model). Next to the documents will appear a highlighted fragment, where the greatest match with the query is found and a link where the user can download the document from its original source. Questions can be formulated in natural language. Users do not need to use any special syntax to search or retrieve documents. It is also possible to filter results by language simply typing in the query: "pdf documents on water saving in Italian". Users can alternatively use the drop-down filters shown under the search window.
- **Testing:** Displays a list of 35 test questions in English and Italian manually prepared by Sigma from documents provided by Holcim to evaluate the system.

- Documents: Returns a list of indexed documents from the configured sources. In the case of Holcim, the number of indexed documents is 20. All of them, are scanned pdf documents.
- Configuration: It allows the user to integrate MetaQuarry with different document management platforms. Credentials obtained from these platforms are stored in a local SQLite database. Currently MetaQuarry is integrated with the following platforms:
 - Google Drive
 - Microsoft SharePoint
 - Owncloud

Natural Language Processing API

The purpose of this module is to provide Natural Language Processing functionalities to improve the search and retrieval of documents and information.

- Language detection
 - This module automatically detects the language of the query when user does not specify the language in his or her query. Detection is done using the SolR Tika component based on a previously trained and highly configurable classifier: recognizable languages can be restricted, only documents in certain languages can be indexed, etc. The language detector recognizes 49 languages with 99% accuracy.
- Query preprocessing
 - Two processes are carried out based on the user's query:
 - Semantic word extraction. It is highly recommended to that you simplify the query and avoid introducing noise, such as very frequent used words of very frequent use or grammatical words: determiners, prepositions, conjunctions, etc. This task is carried out using Spacy POS Tagging pre-trained models.
 - Filter detection. As mentioned above, users can specify the language or format in which they want to filter the results. These entities are recognized in queries by a simple system of rules based on linguistic patterns.

Language model

- As mentioned above, the Question Answering component allows the user to find answers, not just documents. To carry out this functionality, different pretrained language models fine-tuned for the question answering task have been tested and evaluated.
- For each of the languages in which MetaQuarry has been implemented, the model that best answered a series of questions prepared manually based on the documentation provided by the pilot mines has been chosen. The selected models are the following:
 - English: deepset/tinyrobetta-squad2 (HuggingFace, 2023).
 - French: etalab-ia/camembert-base-squadFR-fquad-piaf (HuggingFace, 2023).
 - Italian: anakin87/electra-italian-xxl-cased-squad-it (GitHub, 2023).
 - Spanish: PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-base-bne-sqac (HuggingFace, 2023).

All these models are freely accessible and available on the official website of the HuggingFace project.

The above models return answers explicitly contained in the text, which provides enough security to the user about the reliability of the information provided by the system. However, in many cases the answer that the user is looking for is not explicitly formulated in any particular sentence. In these cases, the question-answer models do not return any information, so they are not very useful.

To solve this issue, the latest version of MetaQuarry has integrated a Large Language Model such as Mixtral1 that allows Abstractive Questions Answering in the languages supported by the project.

Question-answering models have as input, a question, but also a context. The quality of the response therefore depends on two aspects:

- Quality of the prompt. The prompt is the instruction or script someone gives to the model. In the case of Mixtral it is important to specify by means of an appropriate instruction that the answer must be limited to the context provided, obtained from the set of selected documents and the appropriate language. Different versions of the prompt were tested until we found one that minimized hallucinations: text that the model responds to based on information other than that provided in the context.
- Context quality: It is important to accurately select the documents that we provide to the model as a context. If the context provided to the Question Answering model is too small, the model will not find a suitable answer; if it's too big, you won't be able to process it due to the algorithm's limitations.

Depending on the type of documents processed by MetaQuarry (number of pages per document, number of words per page, information in tables, text in images, etc.), we will have to define a longer or shorter context.

The context for the question-answering model is obtained from the most relevant n-documents returned by the search engine, therefore, the quality of the answer ultimately depends on the quality of the search engine.

Advanced Search Engine

The search engine is based on the open-source Apache Solr platform written in Java. The main function of the search engine is to index documents and other sources of information so that they are available from the search engine, once the indexing module has been properly configured. Therefore, this component is responsible for performing both functionalities: the indexing of the information and the retrieval of results.

The functionalities provided by the search engine are:

- Import

From the credentials entered by the user in the local database to using the MetaQuarry configuration tool, the system has access to the documents shared by the user on the various platforms: Google Drive, Microsoft SharePoint or Owncloud. The documents supported by the system are the most common formats of Microsoft Office and Open Office packages: DOC, DOCX, XLS, XLSX, PPT etc.

¹ <https://huggingface.co/mistralai/Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Extract text <p>Once the documents have been temporarily downloaded, the text contained in them is extracted. To do this, the Solr Tika library is used. This tool allows you not only to extract text from the formats mentioned above, but also to process scanned PDF documents and images containing text using OCR optical character recognition technology.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Index <p>The text extracted from each document is indexed using the Solr search engine. Tlf the documents are pageable if they are in : PDF or PPT. Each page is indexed separately to make context selection more efficient. Otherwise, all the document text is indexed in a single entry. In the Holcim pilot, all the documents are PDF type, so that the system has extracted and indexed each page. In total, the Holcim search engine database contains 2,381 entries.</p> <p>If documents are modified or deleted, these documents are automatically updated or removed from the index so that they will not appear as results for new searches.</p>
<p>Target Audience</p>	<p>This service is aimed at helping the quarry managers and operators search in a heterogeneous database of documents for any relevant information they would need for the day-to-day operation of the quarry, quickly finding via natural language quarries text and information “hidden” in almost any type of document (images, scanned pdf, word, power point presentations, excel files, etc.)</p>
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>For this service there is no specific hardware requirement for the quarry if used with the cloud solution form SIGMA. A terminal with internet access is good enough and significant storage capacity is needed if documentation is handled locally.</p> <p>In order to deploy the solution at Sigma premises, a server with two GPUs with 48GB each, for example NVIDIA A6000, is necessary.</p> <p>At the software level, the proposed system is composed of a series of components described below, which will be deployed using open-source Docker technology:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Front-end/Firewall (Apache web server). 2) Web Interface Framework (Streamlit-python). 3) User database (SQLite / PostgreSQL). 4) Search Engine (Apache Solr) 5) Language Models server (vLLM) 6) Component Virtualizer (Docker).
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>To use MetaQuarry, there is no installation required on site for users. It is implemented as a web application and a link is all that is required together with an internet connection.</p>
<p>Communication Protocols -</p>	<p>For the MetaQuarry service, there are no specific connections between devices. Internet protocols are needed to access the web server (HTTPS, basically). The document store implementation depends on the quarry choices, but normally they are implemented on specific commercial platforms as explained above.</p>
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>MetaQuarry can handle a cloud or on-site solution Data security is provided basically by the cloud service providers: Google Drive, Microsoft SharePoint or OwnCloud.</p>

<p>AI Integration & Implementation</p>	<p>For the MetaQuarry service the deployment is being performed on the SIGMA’s infrastructure. One server has been scaled taking into consideration the amount of information provided for the pilots, in this case HOLCIM, but also VICAT has been using the service. The deployment architecture is shown below:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 39. Metaquarry deployment architecture</i></p>
<p>Application Features</p>	<p>The different service web interface pages are shown below:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 40. MetaQuarry user interface (“Questions”)</i></p> <p>The application basically has four windows, one named “Questions” that is being used to insert a query in natural language as shown in the figure above. Then there is the second page named “Testing” that is used to learn how to use the tool by providing example queries relative to the type of documentation handled in HOLCIM.</p>

Figure 41. Metaquery user interface (“Testing”)

The third page, “Documents”, show the available document library as a list. The user can verify what kind of information is being processed by the tool.

Figure 42. MetaQuery user interface (“Documents”)

And finally, there is a fourth “Configuration” page which guides the user on how to include databases/ cloud storage for their documentation that they use internally. This for three commercial solutions:

Google drive

Sharepoint

Owncloud

	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 43. MetaQuarry user interface ("Configuration")</i></p> <p>For each of the three solutions detailed instructions are included.</p> <p>The link that is used to access the MeataQuarry tool for HOLCIM is: https://sigmatag.sigma-ai.com/holcim/</p> <p>The latter is protected with specific credentials.</p>
<p>Security & Compliance</p>	<p>The data from the quarries that is processed will always be protected by the main cloud storage solution that is chosen by the customer. These tools strictly follow state of the art technologies to secure the information and control the authentication process. The latter data (files, documents, etc.) is not sent to any server outside the control of the quarry.</p>
<p>Performance Metrics</p>	<p>The most important metric for such a service is the accuracy in answering and finding the information the user is looking for. The overall accuracy obtained for the HOLCIM set of documentation using MetaQuarry is 96%.</p>
<p>Support & Maintenance</p>	<p>The system is very stable, and up until now the support needed has been minimal. Deployment is autonomous and can be also operated remotely. Troubleshooting until now has needed almost no effort. With respect to maintenance, only server maintenance is needed when detecting issues with their performance, mostly due to memory occupation performance and latency. Until now, no overloading situation has been observed, since the amount of data handled is limited in the pilots. The more information is handled, the better the system dimensioning that must be performed.</p>
<p>Business Model & Pricing</p>	<p>Given the complexity of the technologies developed by the company, commercial management and technical management have always gone hand in hand, both in Sigma's early days and today, to create the sales strategy that Sigma has defined for the commercialization of a new product. As a guideline, the following revenue model is established that will have to be adjusted according to the knowledge acquired in the pilot, and after a more in-depth analysis of market potential. Compared to the initial strategy, prices have been revised due to the current data processing requirements, which have experienced a very significant increase due to the use of LLM models: Pricing associated with Deployment SET-UP: includes the deployment of the platform and integration with the documentary sources to carry out indexing of the documents. Depending on the complexity, a range ranging from €10,000 to €20,000 is forecast. ANNUAL MAINTENANCE: 3.000€. PLATFORM LICENSING: a scenario of</p>

	<p>user steps is conceived, with indicative prices (monthly payment) according to the following table:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Table 5. Pricing structure for metaquarry</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="497 383 1355 663"> <thead> <tr> <th>Users</th> <th>Monthly price</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>From 1 to 100</td> <td>500€</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From 101 to 300</td> <td>800€</td> </tr> <tr> <td>From 301 to 1000</td> <td>1.200€</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Corporate (more than 1000)</td> <td>1.500€</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Users	Monthly price	From 1 to 100	500€	From 101 to 300	800€	From 301 to 1000	1.200€	Corporate (more than 1000)	1.500€
Users	Monthly price										
From 1 to 100	500€										
From 101 to 300	800€										
From 301 to 1000	1.200€										
Corporate (more than 1000)	1.500€										
<p>Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>MetaQuarry will hinge on a modular architecture composed mainly of two components: search engine and web application, now enriched with the use of an LLM model, with which an advanced semantic search tool capable of using natural language as input is implemented.</p> <p>Compared to the solutions present on the market, MetaQuarry has a strong competitive advantage, as it is a new solution that ranges from indexing content to the search engine that will allow the content to be retrieved.</p> <p>In addition, it is a multilingual solution, which analyses content of various types: word, excel, pdf, images, etc. On the other hand, deployment is flexible, it can be on-site or connected through APIs on Sigma's servers, as has been also done in the project.</p> <p>Likewise, the existing solutions on the market today generally do not yet provide a search using natural language but are based on keywords or literal language in the case of search engines implemented in web portals, so MetaQuarry is a very attractive solution for this type of solutions.</p> <p>With MetaQuarry, the daily exploitation of the document base is facilitated by being able to obtain the information in a more intuitive and direct way.</p>										
<p>Future Enhancements</p>	<p>The accuracy of the solution depends now on the LLM technologies employed. And certainly, the model used is key. At the moment, MIXTRAL is being used. But further enhancements can be achieved by using for example the DEEPSEEK MODEL. The latter is still being tested at SIGMA to analyze its performance.</p> <p>Other improvements could be also carried out by applying prompt engineering, introducing a tool that will guide the user on how to better generate queries, using vectorial databases instead of indexation by SolR, or LLM models specialized in Questions-Answering tasks over table information.</p>										

2.5.2.2 Activities performed since November 2023

Basically, for MetaQuarry, only modelling improvements were implemented by for now using the MIXTRAL LLM model, which considerably improved the accuracy of the results.

Moreover, the user interface was also improved in terms of the information and parameters that are shown to the users as explained in the above table.

Finally, an evaluation of the performance in terms of accuracy was performed by inserting queries in Italian and English and evaluating the answers for MetaQuarry.

All the questions in the testing set have had a suitable answer from the language model. For 85% of the questions, the answer is found in the first selected context (30 out of 35), for 11% (4 out of 35), in the second and only one for one question (4% percent) the relevant context to obtain the answer is found in the other documents.

Table 6. Evaluation results for different queries for the HOLCIM database

Question	Answer	Found in (doc. Number)
Where is the the JCI flat screen serial number?	The serial number plate for the JCI Flat Screen is located on page 9 of the provided document.	1
Is there a 24-hour phone number for the JCI flat screen?	Yes, the 24-hour phone number for JCI Parts is 1-888-474-0115.	1
What fastening does the JCI flatscreen use to reduce basket stress?	The JCI flatscreen uses a Huckbolt with a bolt-in deck bracing to reduce deck/basket stress.	1
What is the position of the bottom deck on the JCI flat and combo screens?	The bottom deck on the JCI flat and combo screens is horizontal on both styles of screens.	1
How does the JCI flat screen provide more efficient screening?	The JCI flat screen provides more efficient screening by exposing fine material to a full-sized opening after it has been stratified, unlike an elliptical stroke screen which may not expose the fine material to the full opening due to the nature of its motion.	1
How does the JCI flat screen shaft assembly design reduce stress?	The JCI flat screen's three-shaft design reduces stress by spreading the forcing motion over a larger area, with the center of the basket being the highest stressed area. Additionally, the use of six smaller bearings carrying the load compared to two or four larger ones also improves bearing life.	1
What device must be used when two or more people are working on the same JCI flat screen?	A multiple lockout device must be used when two or more people are working on the same JCI flat screen.	1
What should be done before servicing JCI flat screen machinery powered by diesel engines?	Always disconnect batteries and shut-off fuel supply before servicing the machinery. Lockout/tagout engine controls to ensure that engine is not accidentally started while the machinery is being serviced.	1
When must safety glasses and other PPE be worn?	Safety glasses or goggles should be worn whenever outside of an approved working area around the screen while in operation. MSHA/OSHA approved hard hats, safety glasses, and hearing protection should be worn at all times.	1
What factors may cause JCI flat screen sound levels to vary?	Process material load and operating conditions.	1
Who must approve customer modifications to the JCI flat screen?	JCI Engineering Department must approve any customer-designed support structures for JCI equipment, including modifications to the flat screen.	1

In what weather conditions do precautions need to be taken with wire rope?	Precautions are needed when using wire rope in cold weather, particularly when the rope is frozen.	1
What should be done with trailer tires when parked for an extended period?	When a trailer is parked for an extended period, it's recommended to block the tires to prevent them from rolling or moving.	1
A damaged JCI flat screen was shipped to us. How do we make a claim?	File damage claim form with carrier within 30 days after receiving equipment."	1
The JCI flat screen came without a baseframe. What do we need to install?	If you have a JCI flat screen without a baseframe, you will need to install the following items before running your screen: - Spring Pads - Snubber Assemblies - Tagline Assembly (rubber springs only) - Motor Mount and Drive Assemblies - Belt Guard	1
What should I do with the snubbers before starting the screen?	Before starting the screen, make sure the snubber rubbers are fully retracted into the snubber assemblies. To do this, loosen the jam nut and turn the adjuster bolt counterclockwise. Also, ensure that the snubber assemblies are properly installed and weld them to the support structure/base frame.	1
In what increments can the JCI flat screen stroke angle can be changed?	The JCI flat screen's stroke angle can be changed in 5 degree increments.	1
At what range of degrees can the JCI flat screen stroke angle inclined?	The stroke angle can be changed in 5 degree increments from 30 to 60 degrees of inclination.	2
What is the maximum operating speed of the JCI flat screen?	The maximum operating speed range for the JCI flat screen is 675-875 rpm.	2
What is the optimum belt deflection range when pre-starting the JCI flat screen?	The optimum belt deflection range for pre-starting the JCI flat screen is 4-1/2" (114 mm) at zero degree screen incline angle or 5" (127 mm) at a 10° screen incline angle.	1
How many seconds should it take for the JCI flat screen to reach operating speed?	The JCI flat screen should reach operating speed within 4 to 10 seconds.	1
What is the recommended timing angle for Extra Fine 3/8 Minus at 875 rpm ?	The recommended timing angle for Extra Fine 3/8 Minus at 875 rpm is between 30° and 40°."	1
What is the speed range of the Medium Scalper ?	The speed range for a Medium Scalper screen is 675-875 RPM.	1
ITALIAN		
Quanto rumore fa normalmente l'impianto di frantumazione?	L'impianto di frantumazione é rumoroso per natura intrinseca e il livello di rumorosità durante le operazioni di frantumazione varia da 100 a 110 dB, misurato alla distanza di 1 m dall'impianto di frantumazione stesso.	2
Quale inclinazione deve avere il vaglio vibrante?	L'inclinazione del Vaglio Vibrante Sgrossatore deve essere di 20°.	8

Ogni quanto si deve cambiare l'olio sintetico del motoriduttore?	L'olio sintetico del motoriduttore deve essere sostituito ogni 12.000 ore di lavoro, come indicato nella tabella di manutenzione biennale.	1
Quanto dura la garanzia del vaglio rotante?	La garanzia generale dura un anno, a partire dalla data di spedizione della pompa.	1
Quale distanza di sicurezza deve conservare il personale non autorizzato al vaglio rotante?	Il personale non autorizzato deve essere tenuto a distanza di sicurezza dal Vaglio Rotante (10 mt) mentre la macchina é in funzione lavorativa o in fase di manutenzione.	1
Qual è la produzione massima dell'impianto di prevagliatura?	La produzione massima globale dell'impianto è di 300 t/h, misurata sul trasportatore a nastro di alimentazione primaria.\n	1
Qual è la potenza elettrica installata nella stazione di prevagliatura?	La potenza elettrica installata nella stazione di prevagliatura non è specificata nei documenti forniti."	1
Ogni quanto devo cambiare l'olio dei riduttori?	Il costruttore dei riduttori raccomanda di cambiarlo ogni 400 ore di funzionamento, dal primo avviamento, per garantire la rimozione di eventuali scorie ferrose dalla camera dei rotismi e una lunga durata dei riduttori medesimi.	1
Qual è l'anno di fabbricazione dell'impianto idraulico?	L'anno di fabbricazione dell'impianto idraulico è il 2014.	1
Qual è la portata idrica dell'impianto di lavaggio?	L'impianto di lavaggio è progettato con una portata idrica di 7.000 l/m alla pressione di 2,5 bar.	2
Qual è la potenza elettrica globale installata nell'impianto?	La potenza elettrica complessivamente installata nell'impianto é di 26, kW.	1
A che distanza devo situare il ventilatore del frantoio a cono?	Il ventilatore del frantoio a cono va installato ad una distanza massima di 3,6 m dall'frantoio.	1

2.6 BIM (Task 4.4)

2.6.1 General Summary

Building Information Modeling (BIM) strategies were implemented at HOLCIM Pioltello to create digital representations of the quarry and treatment plant, enhancing visualization and management. This involved developing 3D models of visible plant assets and topography using drone data, photos, and process schemes. A long-term 4D BIM simulation was created with Asta Powerproject, visualizing the documentation and exploitation phases adapted to the site's specific operational characteristics, including dredging and conveyor-based material transport. Furthermore, a 7D model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) was established using Autodesk Tandem, integrating the BIM model with static asset information and dynamic plant production data retrieved from the project's DataLake via a custom integrator, providing a valuable platform for asset monitoring.

2.6.2 Activities performed

Following the initial development reported in Deliverable D4.5, the activities for HOLCIM Pioltello focused on finalizing and deploying the BIM tools:

- **BIM Model Finalization:** The 3D BIM models representing the treatment plant and site topography, developed from available site data, were finalized and prepared in IFC format for integration.

- **4D BIM Plan Finalization:** The long-term 4D BIM plan visualizing the documentation and exploitation phases, tailored to the site's dredging and conveyor operations, was completed within Asta Powerproject.
- **CDE Deployment and Data Integration:** The Common Data Environment (CDE) platform using Autodesk Tandem was deployed for Holcim. This involved uploading the finalized BIM model, incorporating static asset data, and successfully establishing integration with the central DataLake using the custom data integrator. This allowed for the visualization of available dynamic Plant Production data linked to the corresponding assets within the CDE.
- **Training and Handover:** The HOLCIM team received access to the CDE platform, along with initial guidance on utilizing its features for visualizing the plant and the integrated operational data.

2.7 Environmental Performance based on Historical Data (Task 5.4)

For each site, the environmental performance in over 30 environmental impact categories has been calculated using historical data from 2019. A model of the plant has been built in the online web platform, Plantsmith, where all products have been connected to consumption data for the year 2019. Background environmental models have then been used to estimate the environmental performance of each product group. The results have been presented in Deliverable 5.4 for the sites.

Figure 44. Environmental performance simulation

3 Results

The sensors installed in the project allowed for the monitoring and control of data coming from the quarry's sorting and screening plant. This data was crucial not only for the optimal management of the plant during normal working days (an operation directly managed by the quarry manager and the production manager) but also for the analysis and prediction of the performance of the various matrices of interest (hourly, daily, monthly production - efficiency rate - consumption-etc.). In detail, the data analysed and then sent to the data lake / dashboard has unlocked a wealth of information. Key data points include:

Production: Volumes of each product and raw materials fed into the plant.

Energy Consumption: Electrical usage of crushers, vibrating screens, and main water pumps.

Safety: Number of wheel loader-pedestrian interactions.

Resource Management: Fresh and recycled water consumption.

Inventory: Stockpile volumes.

Equipment Performance: Vibrations of the screen.

Operational Times: Start and stop times for the plant and individual machines (crushers and screens).

This data enables the calculation and monitoring of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Defining KPIs precisely is crucial, ensuring data availability and reliability for calculation, and allowing for effective performance monitoring.

The table below outlines the KPIs defined for the Pioltello pilot site.

Table 7. Specific KPIs for Pioltello pilot site.

KPI	Description	Units	Frequency
Average production	Production processed per hour (average)	t/h	day
Raw material production	Total gross production	ton	day
REE	Plant productivity	%	monthly
Stocks level	Total amount of every saleable product	ton	monthly
Total saleable materials	Total saleable materials produced for a certain day	ton	system
Saleable produced	Quantity of finished product divided by type	ton	monthly
Water management - Fresh water	Counter litre from the well pump	Litre	day
Water management - Processing water	Counter litre to the plant	Litre	day
Water management - Recycling water ratio	Counter litre from the well pump/counter litre to the plant	%	day
Energy consumption	Energy consumption of the plant	kWh	system

KPI	Description	Units	Frequency
Energy consumption per gross ton processed	Energy consumed to process a ton of material (total processed material)	kWh/ton	system
Crushing efficiency index	ampere predicted for the predicted amount of fines	a	monthly
Interference index	Interference wheel loader /pedestrian in an area	number	week

3.1 Production

Regarding the production data measured from the beginning of the sensor installation to February 2025, it can be highlighted that the average production tonnage has settled at 235 tons/h, with a trend shown in detail in the graph of Figure 45. As can be seen from the graph, there is a general downward trend in average production from May 2022 to January 2024.

Similarly, analysing the raw material production data (Figure 46), the trend towards a decrease in the quantities produced is confirmed, also present in the previous graph.

This variability actually depends on several factors, such as, specifically, the quality of the material processed. In fact, the quarry is progressively exhausting the authorized excavation volumes, digging deeper and deeper into finer and partly clay materials, and is awaiting new excavation permits.

Examining the REE data (Figure 47), however, it is evident that during the project duration, the trend is improving by about 10 percentage points (from 75% to 85%), demonstrating that the sensors and the digitized management of the plant, even net of the important variables mentioned above such as the worsening of the quality of the excavated material, have led to a better overall efficiency. This fact is evident even if we compare the data of the reference year (2019) where the average REE was around 80%.

Figure 45. Monthly average hourly production (ton/h) of Pioltello plant. In blue is reported the trending line.

Figure 46. Monthly production of the plant (t). In blue is reported the trending line.

Figure 47. Monthly Running Equipment Effectiveness (REE) of the plant. In blue is reported the trending line.

The authorization situation, previously mentioned, has also affected the presence of material stocks on the ground which, as can be seen in Figure 48, has undergone a sharp decrease in the quantities of finished materials stored.

In an area close to Milan Linate airport, and therefore subject to air traffic control, inventory detection using drones is not easily applicable due to the restrictions imposed. In our site, the installation of fixed cameras and/or detection through dedicated mobile phone applications is easier to implement.

The presence of volumetric sensors positioned on the finished product belts has allowed for constant monitoring and control of the plant's production, enabling better planning of both production and sales policies.

As an example, the figures below show the total monthly production trends for materials for the year 2024 (Figure 49) and the representation for natural products (Figure 50) and for crushed products (Figure 51).

Figure 48. Stockpiles volume saleables materials

Figure 49. Monthly total saleable materials - year 2024.

Figure 50. Monthly saleable materials by type of natural products- year 2024

Figure 51. Monthly saleable materials by type of crushing products – year 2024

3.2 Water

Water is used at the Pioltello plant in the production process to wash and screen aggregates to produce high-quality finished products. The plant is equipped with a purification system that separates fine particles from process water and recycles the purified water back into production.

Regarding water consumption, it has been found that, since the beginning of the project, the total amount of water used by the plant for production has been around 66,700 cubic meters. The clean water drawn from the well and used to replenish the water supply has been, on average, around 8,100 cubic meters per month. This has resulted, for the period under review, in a water recycling rate of approximately 87%.

Figure 52 shows a comparison of the water recycling rate between 2019 (reference year) and 2024. As can be seen from the graph, the use of sensors applied to the plant has allowed for an increase in the water recycling rate by an average of almost 0.2 percentage points. If the last two months of 2024 are excluded (where processing was affected by the presence of very fine materials), the recycling rate has had an average increase of about 1.2 percentage points.

Regarding the water consumption used per ton produced (Figure 54), a substantial alignment of the values found for the two years analysed is noted (except for the last two months of 2024 for the reasons mentioned above).

Finally, it is worth noting that the water factor is subject, more than others, to extreme variability linked mainly to the quality of the material extracted and therefore sent for processing. Material richer in fines requires a greater amount of process water (washing and screening) to reach the quality standards required by the market.

Figure 52. Comparative system delivery water for the year 2024

Figure 53. Recycling water ratio: comparative year 2019 - year 2024

Figure 54. Water consumption per ton processed: comparative year 2019 - year 2024

3.3 Energy

The installed sensors have allowed for a detailed analysis of the plant's energy consumption, breaking down the total consumption by processing phases (process and extraction - Figure 55). Figure 55.

More specifically (Figure 56), the consumption of only the selection and screening plant per ton processed has been highlighted, comparing the reference year 2019 with the last production year 2024.

The graph shows that there has been an average increase in the energy required to produce one ton of material of about 0.11 kWh/t.

This data is however affected by the authorization and material quality issues already expressed previously.

Figure 55. Energy consumption of the plant (kWh) for the year 2024.

Figure 56. Energy consumption per ton processed (kWh/t): comparative year 2019 - year 2024

3.4 Crushing

As previously mentioned in point 2.1 of this report, two Q-vision systems were installed, one before the crushing process and one after, which allowed us to assess the effectiveness of the crushing system and, in case of anomalies, proceed with its setting to optimize its yield.

Figure 57 shows an excerpt of the graph comparing the fineness modules of the material before and after crushing. From this data, it was possible to determine that the average crushing efficiency was approximately 2 points of fineness modules.

Figure 57. Fineness modules crushing plant: comparison of incoming and outgoing materials

The following figure (Figure 58) shows a portion of the data, extracted from the installed sensors, comparing the reduction in fineness modulus with the crusher motor power consumption.

Figure 58. Comparative fineness module reduction (blue line) - engine absorption (orange line)

3.5 Safety

The installation of cameras on the wheel loaders made it possible to monitor the interferences between wheel loaders and pedestrian that were detected during the project and then carry out the analysis of the results. As an example, in Figure 59 the map with the interference points found in the year 2024 is shown, each red point corresponds to an interference detected.

The same data from the previous figure were then reported in the table and represented in figure 55, from these data it can be seen that the greatest number of interferences were detected in the first four months of the year, subsequently, following the segregation of the routes (wheel loaders / pedestrian routes) the number of interferences significantly decreased.

Figure 59. Map of interferences wheel loader / pedestrian – year 2024

Figure 60. Interferences index wheel loader / pedestrian per week – year 2024

4 Conclusions and recommendations

The Pioltello pilot site has implemented, installed, and successfully tested all the sensors foreseen by the project related to the treatment of alluvial sand and gravel materials.

Specifically, the activity focused are related to:

- Quarry plant processing: (selection, washing, and primary crushing, measurement of production and storage)
- Consumption measurement and management: (electricity, water intake, diesel fuel) to reduce the overall impact of the activity on environmental and social aspects.
- Management and control of the interaction between heavy machinery (front loaders) and workers: for safety and health purposes.

Another fundamental part of the project was the on-site realization of the connections between the IOT - PLC - SCADA quarry sensor part and the cloud Data Lake - Data warehouse - Dashboard part. Infact, the aspect of connecting information starting from the quarry is not a secondary issue, as there are often difficulties in connecting between extraction areas and network systems (Wi-Fi, internet connection, etc.).

In general, the data collection and analysis process has shown that it is essential for a complete and better management of the production process (selection, screening, and crushing) to have the entire process integrated and digitalized.

The data collection work carried out in these years of the project is of fundamental importance not only for the daily management of the plant but also because it constitutes a solid data base useful for the next years of production of the plant.

The data has shown that in a complex system with many variables like that of a quarry processing plant, the longer the measurement period, the more complete the data analysis and its understanding. In the specific case of Pioltello, for example, compared to the initial project target objectives, we realized that the lithological variations of the sand and gravel deposit (both areal and in depth) influence the measured results and that therefore a longer measurement period than the duration of this project would be necessary.

Even aspects not directly related to the technical production part, not foreseen at the beginning, can be very important in the data results. For example, we refer to the part of authorizations (timing and duration) which in this specific case have had a direct influence on the volumes extracted and therefore processed at the production plant.

Generally, during the project period, the main results achieved, demonstrating the effectiveness of the project itself, were those related to the improvement of:

- Plant efficiency: as previously illustrated, the REE data during the project duration has seen a trend increase of 10 percentage points.
- Water recycling: also, for this aspect, the improvement compared to the data of the reference year has seen an average increase of about 2 percentage points.
- Crushing control: the applied sensors have allowed for better management of the crushing system, allowing for prompt intervention on the machine settings.

Finally, the safety aspect should be considered, as the tested technologies have allowed us to understand how to best manage the human-machine interaction and configure the internal traffic management in the best way, separating pedestrian paths from those of heavy machinery movements.

Success factors

The project's success factor is linked to the fact that the technologies used are easy to install and use, and above all, allow for direct support in the quarry through instant feedback of the data collected.

Our group has already replicated some technologies related to the sensor part for production optimization and plant management in two other sand and gravel quarries in Italy. The same camera technology used by the DEQ project was also used for the H&S purpose, for active monitoring of the ramp in a concrete plant.

The main barriers identified are related to the training of new professionals in the quarry sector. It will be necessary to invest in the training of quarry operators for the analysis of the data collected, as the optimal management of these systems, for optimal functioning, must be managed directly by quarry operators and not carried out, perhaps afterwards and remotely, by a supervisor.

Another point to pay attention to concerns the maintenance of the installed systems which, in difficult environments like those of quarries with the presence of dust and vibrations, must be constant and punctual in order to guarantee the constant and precise collection of reliable data.

Future Outlook

The main recommendation is to equip yourself with a single data management platform that can be shared with other potential sites and can be expanded or modified as needed.

Integration with administrative management systems (such as SAP) could be considered to unify the accounting of production/sales data by automating month-end closures, focusing primarily on the part of recording the quantities of materials processed and comparing saleable products.

The installed systems have also been very useful in supporting the environmental sustainability aspect by helping in the management of resources (raw materials) through consumption control (i.e. energy, consumables, water, waste, etc).

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